

24th WICAL TRANSCENDING DIALOGUES

28-30 June 2022 | Online

SINCE 1997

**24th Warwick International Conference
in Applied Linguistics, University of Warwick**

The background features a complex pattern of thin, overlapping wavy lines in shades of blue and purple. Scattered throughout are various sized circles in light blue, orange, grey, yellow, and purple. A horizontal bar with four colored segments (blue, orange, grey, yellow) is positioned below the text.

Day 1: 28th June

24th WICAL

TRANSCENDING DIALOGUES

DAY 1: 28 June 2022 | Online

8:30	Opening (main room)	<p>Conference opening Prof. Ema Ushioda, <i>Professor and Head of Department, Department of Applied Linguistics, Warwick University</i> & WICAL Committee</p>
8:50	Workshop (main room)	<p>'You look too happy to be a PhD student' — Some autoethnographic reflections Dr. Wang Zi, <i>Internationalisation Coordinator in Student Opportunity, University of Warwick</i></p>
10:20		
10:40	Workshop (main room)	<p>Supporting teachers to research their classrooms Prof. Richard Smith, <i>Professor at the Department of Applied Linguistics, University of Warwick</i></p>
12:10	Lunch Break (Wonder room)	Speed networking
13:00	Workshop (main room)	<p>Some complex ethical issues when working with participants under 18 years of age Dr. Annamaria Pinter, <i>Reader at the Department of Applied Linguistics, University of Warwick</i></p>
14:30		
14:50	Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 1)	<p>Xiaofang Lu Pre-service Language Teacher Identity Construction in Practice and in Discourse Meifang Zhuo A qualitative exploration of a workshop-based plan of teacher development for English language teaching professionals in China Bochra Kouraichi Estonian Students' LOTE Motivation</p>
	Discourse Analysis (parallel, room 2)	<p>Kerrilyn Jackson Death row final statements: a move-based account with consideration of grammatical and pragmatic features Xiaohong Hu A Genre-Based Analysis of Move-Step Structure of Introduction in Master's Theses Zhiyi Liu (Co-)constructing an adult child's/older sister's identities: Membership categorization analysis of Chinese-Australian family talk</p>
16:30		

24th WICAL

TRANSCENDING DIALOGUES

DAY 1: 28 June 2022 | Online

14:50

Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 3)

Zhiming Yang | How Communication Strategies Influence Chinese Overseas Undergraduates' Willingness to Communicate and Anxiety.
Yiyang Yang | The efficacy of corpus-based error resolution on EAP writing development in a classroom-based tertiary FL context in China.
Samira Khodadadi | Multimodality in online classrooms: Effects on students' behavioral engagement

16:30

Intercultural Communication (parallel, room 4)

Angelina Barbasheva | Approaches to creating linguistic inclusivity for people with non-binary and transgender identities
Chen Jialu | An Empirical Analysis of Formulaic Expressions in ELF—Taking Body Parts Vocabulary as Examples
Nour Elhouda Souleh | Nour Elhouda Souleh: Stand-up Comedy as a Subversive Site for Learning

16:50

Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 1)

Aidana Kuanyshkaliyeva | Writing is the most complicated skill for ESL learners, and how can it be improved
Amirhossein Mohammadi Meshgini | The Effect of Web-based Interventionist Dynamic Assessment on Iranian EFL Learners' Writing Fluency

Discourse Analysis (parallel, room 2)

Zhen Yang | Refugee Narratives: World University Service's Ethiopian and Eritrean Scholarship Programmes in the Light of Current Practice
Alex Christiansen | Social Media, Imagery and Text: A Corpus-based Multimodal Discourse Analysis of Inauthentic Twitter Users

Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 3)

Yimei Mi | Research on the impact of having native English speaker teachers in Chinese kindergarten from the perspectives of teachers and parents
Ting SU | Student Teachers' Application of the CLT Approach During Teacher Practicum in Mainland China-Through the Lens of Transfer Climate

18:00

Discourse Analysis (parallel, room 4)

Ju WAN | A Study on English-Chinese Translation of Forensic Shakespeare from the Perspective of Logic Translation Theory
Jilan Wei | Who knows better: Corpus-assisted discourse analysis of 'I know' in the UK government announcements during the pandemic

DAY 1: 28 June 2022

08:50-10:20 | Workshop | Main room

Dr. Wang Zi | *Internationalisation Coordinator in Student Opportunity, University of Warwick*

‘You look too happy to be a PhD student’ — Some autoethnographic reflections

Dear postgraduate students, have you ever felt lost, lost motivation, or doubted yourself? You are not alone! In this workshop, I will use personal stories from my autoethnographic data – which includes personal journals and social media posts from 2017 to 2022 – and share reflections on my PhD journey. My reflections will focus on such aspects of doing a PhD degree as task and time management, work-life balance, and self-regulation of motivation. This workshop also includes interactive activities for you to get to know each other, reflect on your own motivational ups and downs, and try out some strategies I personally find useful. There will be a Q&A session towards the end of the workshop, so come along with your questions!

Dr Wang Zi has a PhD degree (awarded in February 2022) in English Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics from the Department of Applied Linguistics, University of Warwick. She currently works as Internationalisation Coordinator in Student Opportunity at Warwick and manages the university’s intercultural training project. Her research interests include motivation, language learning, and multilingualism. Her PhD thesis investigates Chinese learners’ motivation to learn English and Japanese and is titled ‘Being and becoming: An ecological exploration of humanistic motivation in multilingual learning among Japanese language majors in China’. Her most recent first-authored publication (Wang, McConachy, & Ushioda, 2021) is titled ‘Negotiating identity tensions in multilingual learning in China: A situated perspective on language learning motivation and multilingual identity’.

DAY 1: 28 June 2022

10:40-12:10 | Workshop | Main room

Prof. Richard Smith | *Professor at the Department of Applied Linguistics, University of Warwick*

Supporting teachers to research their classrooms

In the field of language education, most PhD students, along with early-career and established academics, want their research to be of use, i.e. want their research to have a positive impact. However, we also know that teachers rarely read research theses or articles, finding them inaccessible and/or impenetrable. We begin, then, by considering whether/how this kind of barrier can be overcome.

Many suggestions seem to position teachers as consumers of research rather than engaging them in research to meet their own real needs. Different forms of participatory research will, then, be briefly discussed, from the point of view of how they can involve practising teachers as active agents.

The main focus of the workshop, however, will be on how teachers can be supported to do their own practitioner research – research by teachers, for teachers, as this has sometimes been sloganised in the context of the British Council's Champion Teachers programme in Latin America. Lessons from this programme will be shared, in particular regarding how academic norms may need to be subverted if teachers are to do feasible, useful and empowering research ([Smith & Rebolledo, 2018](#)).

In this connection, how to mentor teacher-research has emerged as a particularly important area of interest within programmes like Champion Teachers and the Action Research Mentoring Scheme in India and Nepal (cf. [Smith, 2020](#)). The workshop ends with practical insights relating, specifically, to teacher-research mentoring.

Assuming that current PhD students are educational leaders of the future, the workshop should help them to conceive of engaging teachers as active agents in practitioner research and/or participatory research, not only attempting to engage them with academic research as consumers in years to come.

Dr Richard Smith (Professor of ELT & Applied Linguistics, University of Warwick) has carried out research in the fields of history of language learning and teaching, learner autonomy and teacher development. In this last area, he is known particularly for his practical work supporting teachers of English in public education systems in countries of the Global South, as founder and former coordinator of the Teaching English in Large Classes network (bit.ly/telnet-home), and as academic adviser to teacher-research programmes in Latin America (Champion Teachers) and South Asia (ARMS). In the last two of these roles, he developed the Exploratory Action Research approach to teacher development which he has shared in two Open Access publications: *A Handbook for Exploratory Action Research* (with Paula Rebolledo) and *Mentoring Teachers to Research Their Classrooms: A Practical Handbook*. Further information: <http://www.warwick.ac.uk/richardcsmith>

DAY 1: 28 June 2022

13:00-14:30 | Workshop | Main room

Dr. Annamaria Pinter | *Reader at the Department of Applied Linguistics, University of Warwick*

Some complex ethical issues when working with participants under 18 years of age

In this workshop I will explore challenges that researchers face who decide to work with participants aged 18 or under. Contrasting priorities resulting from researchers' desire to engage these learners fully on the one hand and to protect them on the other hand lead to some difficult dilemmas. I will explore both macro and micro-ethical issues while giving the workshop participants a chance to reflect on their own experiences (if they have any). The workshop will conclude with some guidelines for conducting ethical research with this population.

Annamaria Pinter is a Reader at the Department of Applied Linguistics, the University of Warwick, UK. Her research interests focus on all aspects of second/ foreign language education for children, task-based second language teaching and learning and engaging children actively in research. She has published widely in the area of teaching English to children and has a strong international reputation in TEYL and second language teacher education. She is the author of *Teaching Young Language Learners Oxford Handbooks for Language Teachers*, Oxford University Press (second edition, 2017), *Children Learning Second Languages*, Palgrave Macmillan (2011), and joint series editor of *Early Language Learning in School Contexts* by Multilingual Matters.

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 1: 14:50-16:30 | Parallel room 1

Xiaofang Lu | Pre-service Language Teacher Identity Construction in Practice and in Discourse

Teacher identity is conceptualized as an ongoing process of learning to become. However, little attention has been paid to the pre-service teacher identity, and fewer studies focus on the development of language teacher identity (Foley, Anderson, Hancock & Conteh, 2022). The formation on teacher identity is a complex, and it is hard to theorize the process in merely one framework, because this would lead only to partial views on identity formation. In this presentation, I will discuss the potential theoretical framework for understanding the construction of language teacher identity in a multidimensional way, that is identity-in-practice and identity-in-discourse.

With the aim of understanding teacher identity formation, the expected outcome for the study is to contribute possible pedagogical and theoretical implications for pre-service teachers that will produce a comprehensive understanding of “what” the process of continuous becoming is; “why” teacher identity is formed in such a ways, and “how” better to fit aspects of personal identities with professional identities in response to various sociocultural and sociopolitical influences.

Meifang Zhuo | A qualitative exploration of a workshop-based plan of teacher development for English language teaching professionals in China

"The potential of teacher research for Continuing Professional Development (CPD) has been validated in a range of language teacher education projects across the world (Smith et al., 2014; Hanks & Dikilitaş, 2018). To date, however, most of these projects adopt only either exploratory practice (EP) or action research (AR) (Burns, 2010), or an emerging innovative initiative termed ‘exploratory action research (EAR)’ (Smith et al., 2014; Rebolledo et al., 2016; Smith, 2015), a pinch of exportation into AR."

The study aims to find out teachers' views on EP/AR/(EP+AR) for CPD and the immediate and long-term impacts of the innovative proposal (EP+AR) on teacher development.

Social media: <https://twitter.com/ZhuoMeifang> | *I'd love to have a dialogue about: teacher development, exploratory practice and action research*

Bochra Kouraichi | Estonian Students' LOTE Motivation

The present study relies on 68 narratives of Estonian learners of French, Finnish, German, Spanish and Italian as a major or minor at university level. It aims to explore the motivation of Estonian university students to learn foreign languages other than English (LOTE).

The ideal L2 self as well as the L2 learning experience were the most important in developing and maintaining students' motivation. Students' ultimate goals were mainly study abroad programs and relocation in a foreign country after graduation. Both the context and the population of this study are new since language learning motivation has received little attention by Estonian scholars.

Discourse Analysis

DAY 1: 14:50-16:30 | Parallel room 2

Kerrilyn Jackson | Death row final statements: a move-based account with consideration of grammatical and pragmatic features

This paper analyses final statements made by prisoners primarily on death row in the US from a mixed-framework approach. Starting with an English for Specific Purposes (ESP) perspective (Swales, 1990), this study seeks to describe the function of moves and their individual steps by combining knowledge from the pragmatics-led fields of Systemic Functional Linguistics and Speech Act Theory. This mixed approach ultimately allows for a detailed description of final statements which fuses together three different perspectives: structural, grammatical, and pragmatic.

In a previous paper (Author, 2017), I concluded that there is a range of communicative purposes for this genre which are typically realised by including one or more moves out of a set of four core moves. The four core moves include: apologising to others, expressing love, making a religious reference, and thanking. I argue that the move-based account can be re-evaluated and expanded upon in order to make a meaningful contribution to the fields of genre studies by examining a 'lay' genre.

Xiaohong Hu | A Genre-Based Analysis of Move-Step Structure of Introduction in Master's Theses

There have been an increasing number of discourse studies on the writing of introduction to published research articles. However, little attention is given to the introduction to student-produced academic genres, especially for the master's thesis. Therefore, the present study aims to describe how masters majoring in applied linguistics write their thesis introductions in general and further to figure out how subject specialists think about the disciplinary norms of introduction writing and instruct students to finish their theses.

A preliminary discourse analysis has revealed that most of the thesis introductions contain moves and steps prescribed by the model and show features like cyclicity and embedding. New moves and steps are also spotted, such as presenting positive justification and revealing personal motivation. A full comparative analysis and semi-structured interviews will be conducted to complement the overall analysis of thesis introductions. Suggestions for future research and genre-based language teaching are provided in order to enhance master's thesis writing.

Zhiyi Liu | (Co-)constructing an adult child's/older sister's identities: Membership categorization analysis of Chinese-Australian family talk

Identity is viewed as a discursive accomplishment constructed in and enacted through ongoing social interaction (Benwell & Stokoe, 2006), which is a widely researched topic in the area of pragmatics. Identity studies in family discourse have primarily focused on doing 'being parents' in family life, whereas child identity and sibling identity have received less attention. Therefore, by looking at approximately 15-hour audio-recorded family conversations in a Chinese-Australian family, this study aims to contribute to such an underexplored area by investigating how specific identities are invoked by and/or ascribed to an adult child/older sister during different family activities.

In the findings, two specific memberships, namely as a home educator and as a child, are invoked, ascribed and negotiated between participants via self- and other-categorization in (mostly) mother-children conversations. More specifically, while the adult child/older sister invokes her memberships via her displaying rights, responsibilities, or other attributes that are packaged in such categories in the design and formulation of social actions, how other participants categorize her is heard from the way in which they react with her self-categorization in the following turn. This study provides us with an insight into identity construction of children and/or siblings in family talk in general.

Social media: https://twitter.com/zhiyi_liu21

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 1: 14:50-16:30 | Parallel room 3

Zhiming Yang | How Communication Strategies Influence Chinese Overseas Undergraduates' Willingness to Communicate and Anxiety

Although there has been a great deal of research on English language learning in an EFL/ESL context, it can be noticed that the focuses are largely on pedagogical perspectives in a monolingual language environment in the classroom. Besides, few studies have investigated the experience of overseas students at British universities. The present study attempts to explore the effects of Communication strategies (CSs) on Chinese overseas undergraduates' willingness to communicate (WTC) and anxiety in three scenarios: in the classroom, outside the classroom and online. It aims to know to what extent Chinese undergraduates find CSs helpful for increasing their WTC and relieving their anxiety during daily communications.

Results indicated that participants felt more relaxed during communication as it helped them to make conversation easier and more natural when problems occurred, and to expand their lexicon. While it may not help them to feel confident about their language abilities, it is not helpful when they continuously fail to understand what the others are saying. It is hoped that this study on exploring the possible influence of CSs on students' anxiety and WTC may help language teachers or researchers to enhance the educational curriculum for the purpose of facilitating students' oral performance as well as their language learning with confidence within an overseas environment.

Social media: https://twitter.com/viola_yang0716 | I'd love to have a dialogue about: communication strategies, pragmatics

Yiyang Yang | The efficacy of corpus-based error resolution on EAP writing development in a classroom-based tertiary FL context in China

Although written corrective feedback (WCF) has been discussed for several decades, the effectiveness of WCF remains arguable based on different factors. One aim of the study is to explore the efficacy of indirect WCF in conjunction with the corpus-based self-correction method, especially for lexical errors, on EAP writing development and language acquisition in the target classrooms. Another is to identify potential challenges of implementing the corpus in a classroom-based foreign language (FL) context for language teachers.

The preliminary results reveal that the corpus-based method facilitated language learning by allowing students to seek linguistic patterns, enhance lexical knowledge and writing accuracy, and modifying the writing habit of word selection and Chinese-English direct translation. The challenges that FL teachers might face when employing a corpus include 1) assisting learners to key-in appropriate KWIC (Key Word in Context) in a corpus and develop learners' data analytical skills in filtering the corpus output, 2) delivering clear WCF codes, 3) providing sufficient corpus-based training/instructions, 4) boosting learners' efficiency. Evidence on the effects of scaffolding in the corpus-based error revision process has emerged from the data.

Social media: <https://twitter.com/Camelliayang>

Samira Khodadadi | Multimodality in online classrooms: Effects on students' behavioral engagement

One of the challenges in online classes would be engaging students as effectively as in face-to-face learning. Multimodality in which different forms of communication are combined can influence the students' engagement and we can expect that by augmenting the number of modes of communication, the students' attention, emotions, and behavior and finally, engagement enhance. In this research, we studied the effects of multimodality on students' behavioral engagement.

We observed that the student's behavioral engagement in the first class was the lowest, but there weren't any significant differences between the students' behavioral engagement in the second and third classes. The findings suggest that augmenting the number of content-related modes might have an influence on the students' behavioral engagement.

Intercultural Communication

DAY 1: 14:50-16:30 | Parallel room 4

Angelina Barbasheva | Approaches to creating linguistic inclusivity for people with non-binary and transgender identities

The new understanding of gender and its expression needs to be translated into language. However, modern Russian and English only describe two genders. Scientific and official styles also carry gender biases. One of the reasons for this is the lack of systematized information regarding the expression of non-binary and transgender identities. Thus, individuals whose gender identities move out of the binary system are left without linguistic representation. Purpose: to systematize and classify the language features of transgender and non-binary persons. Objectives: to indicate the visibility of non-binary and transgender persons in gender-inclusive language and to integrate developed linguistic structures into familiar patterns.

Through analyzing the missing points in English and Russian speaking gender linguistic studies, we have found new gender-inclusive categories in both languages. Thus, we managed to track the direction towards which given gender-inclusive categories expand. Using gathered information, we have developed classification which observes variants of inclusivity in English and Russian and outlines the differences and similarities of grammatical, lexical, phonetic and graphical forms. Advancement of such systematization is aimed at simplifying the perception of new linguistic forms, and raising the issue of non-binary and transgender categories in language to the level of study in general linguistics.

Social media: https://twitter.com/gelya_cool_bb | I'd love to have a dialogue about: gender linguistics, gender-inclusive language, queer linguistics

Chen Jialu | An Empirical Analysis of Formulaic Expressions in ELF—Taking Body Parts Vocabulary as Examples

The growing body of descriptive ELF (English as Lingua Franca) research now is turning the interest on the account of ELF nature of its non-standard, variability and creativity. The current paper tries to prove that the non-conformist usage in ELF can not be interpreted not as evidence of incompetence, contributing to the understanding of the difference in formulaic expressions used between native and ELF interlocutors, and the what extent the Idiom Principle is employed.

It concludes that Idiom Principle in ELF is still the salient guiding mechanism as formulaic expressions serve as references for their holistic possessing advantage. Moreover, there is tendency toward situationally temporary formula such as “sour face”, “get a knock on their heads”, “mind-blowing”, “tiger face” co-constructed in ongoing interactions, which do not seem to cause communication breakdowns, but instead, implying that ELF speakers with different sociocultural backgrounds can be pragmatically effective by creating emergent common ground.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: intercultural communication, paper writing

Nour Elhouda Souleh: Stand-up Comedy as a Subversive Site for Learning

This research presentation attempts to transcend the demeaning notion surrounding research in humour or using comedic discourse. In the reconsideration of the potential of stand-up comedy in academic research, I ground my arguments surrounding its importance in encountering Othering and creating space for learning about the Self and Others.

The presentation starts by introducing the different theoretical possibilities that explore the potential of stand-up comedic materials with a focus on the intercultural lens. This latter is grounded in Holliday's work surrounding small cultures, competing worlds and narratives (2021). This assists in unpacking the notion of Othering and contributes to the process of “unlearning” stereotypes (Cochran-Smith, 2002; Gola, 2021). This is why; other theoretical acuties relating to the use of stand-up comedy in research include Feminist and Decolonial thought.

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 1: 16:50-18:00 | Parallel room 1

Aidana Kuanyshkaliyeva | Writing is the most complicated skill for ESL learners, and how can it be improved

Writing was considered as one of the difficult skills to acquire by Grade 9 EFL (English as a foreign language) students in one of the Kazakhstani schools in 2020 . This challenge has been identified in their formative and summative assessments works. The points they gained in their exam papers were lower than in other skills. In the student's writing except for grammar and vocabulary errors, there were issues concerned with reasoning, organisation as the most important element, and argumentation. Several strategies were offered, two main areas were chosen to improve: functional literacy and expanding the awareness of identifying the arguments in a written piece of writing.

It took a whole term to investigate whether the platform impacts their writing skills. Students were responsible to read the assigned articles daily, take down the new vocabulary and write a summary of the articles in the provided book of knowledge. Later in class for the warming-up activity students shared with their interesting information read, some facts and new words. While reading the articles they tend to identify writer's main idea and supporting arguments. Additionally, it can expand to investigate writer's purpose and empower the sentence structure, such as using the clauses. Overall, students have found this platform useful to improve writing and analytical skills.

Social media: <https://uk.linkedin.com/in/aidana-kuanyshkaliyeva-3b0b60165> | *I'd love to have a dialogue about: teaching ESL students*

Amirhossein Mohammadi Meshgini | The Effect of Web-based Interventionist Dynamic Assessment on Iranian EFL Learners' Writing Fluency

This study can give useful hints to EFL researchers in selecting good topics for their future studies. Also, it bridges a gap in the literature. It helps EFL learners to develop their critical thinking and imitate the style of other writers. To this end, the objective of this study is two-folded: 1. Investigating the effect of web-based interventionist dynamic assessment on Iranian EFL learners' writing fluency 2. Exploring Iranian EFL learners' perceptions of web-based interventionist dynamic assessment.

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that using web-based interventionist DA can be beneficial for EFL learners to improve their writing fluency. Taking the findings into account, it is also concluded that web-based interventionist DA can be considered as an appropriate way for making writing fluency easier for EFL learners due to scaffolding and hints provided for the learners in the treatment sessions.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: Interventionist Dynamic Assessment, Iranian EFL learners, Web-based Dynamic assessment

Discourse Analysis

DAY 1: 16:50-18:00 | Parallel room 2

Zhen Yang | Refugee Narratives: World University Service's Ethiopian and Eritrean Scholarship Programmes in the Light of Current Practice

Studies have shown that Higher Education (HE) provides refugees with an indispensable pathway to gain employment, rebuild professional identity and resettle in the host society. This project will focus on refugees' higher education access and participation by comparing a UK-based programme, World University Service's training scholarships for Ethiopians and Eritreans from 1970s to the 1990s with practice of a NGO named ReConnect nowadays. The research aims to explore how such engagements impact refugees' resettlement and integration, identity negotiation, and then how these can be perceived as 'empowering' at different levels.

The project will understand refugees' personal experiences and perspectives of engaging in higher education programmes and extend the practice of hearing voices of refugees. It will also contribute to the work on refugee educational and professional development support programmes both in the UK and other refugee diasporas by investigating the existed support mechanisms.

Social media: <https://uk.linkedin.com/in/aidana-kuanyshkaliyeva-3b0b60165> | *I'd love to have a dialogue about: teaching ESL students*

Alex Christiansen | Social Media, Imagery and Text: A Corpus-based Multimodal Discourse Analysis of Inauthentic Twitter Users

Despite its inherent multimodal nature, large-scale analytical work looking at social media has remained primarily mono-modal and text-focused, with multimodal work still in its infancy (Knight 2011: 392; Knight 2015: 20). The proposed paper uses initial results from my Ph.D. to present a brief overview of the challenges presented by large-scale multimodal analysis and how this relates particularly to social media. In addition, the study itself gives into the multimodal discourse features of an 'inauthentic' user group, namely Russians trying to perform election interference on Twitter, and how this differs from 'authentic' user content.

The paper highlights why researchers should analyse social media data multimodally and gives some initial options for how we might do so. The results of the analysis highlight the distinct discourse practices of an 'inauthentic' discourse community on social media and give further insights into how Russian state-backed entities attempted to affect both UK and US elections in 2016 and 2020 e.g., by manipulating activist communities such as Black Lives Matter and by serving as a tool of amplification to rightwing conservative communities such as Leave EU.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: multimodality, Corpus Linguistics, Online Communication

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 1: 16:50-18:00 | Parallel room 3

Yimei Mi | Research on the impact of having native English speaker teachers in Chinese kindergarten from the perspectives of teachers and parents

There are diverse ways of teaching and learning English to young learners. Chinese English teachers and foreign English teachers, including native English speakers and non-native English speakers, are both very common in China. This study focuses on the impact of having native English speaker teachers in Chinese kindergarten from the perspectives of teachers and parents as there are few studies concentrating on this topic in the specific context of early years education in China.

From findings of this study, some parents preferred their children study English with native English speaker teachers while others do not consider there is any difference between NESTs and Non-NESTs when teaching English in Chinese kindergarten. The teachers thought it was better to combine the NESTs and Non-NESTs together because they both have different advantages and disadvantages. Sometimes the NESTs needed the assistant of Chinese English teachers when having lessons in kindergarten. The administrator of the specific kindergarten confirmed this finding by emphasizing that the relationship between NESTs and Non-NESTs was complementary.

Social media: <https://uk.linkedin.com/in/aidana-kuanyshkaliyeva-3b0b60165> | *I'd love to have a dialogue about: teaching ESL students*

Ting SU | Student Teachers' Application of the CLT Approach During Teacher Practicum in Mainland China-Through the Lens of Transfer Climate

The study, adopting the transfer climate scale model proposed by Holton et al. (1998) as the theoretical framework, investigates whether the features of the transfer climate within the practicum schools facilitate or hamper the student teachers' implementation of the Communicative Language Teaching approach (CLT) during the practicum and the theory-practice gap in teacher education in Mainland China.

(1) The findings of the present study unveiled several contextual constraints which interfered with the student teachers' adoption of the CLT approach. The contextual constraints could be further categorized into three clusters: the nature of high-stake college entrance exam; students' socialization patterns and limited English proficiency; large class size (2) The findings of the research showed the disparities between the theory-based, abstract and general expert knowledge rendered in the teacher education program and the action-guiding knowledge.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: English teaching approach; CLT; transfer climate

Discourse Analysis

DAY 1: 16:50-18:00 | Parallel room 4

Ju WAN | A Study on English-Chinese Translation of Forensic Shakespeare from the Perspective of Logic Translation Theory

This study examines the English-Chinese translation of forensic Shakespeare from the perspective of Logic Translation Theory.

Translation is a logical activity, but little attention has been paid to the translation of logic. Forensic rhetoric deals with accuse or defend, which requires clarity of thought and logic in order to get the audience's or judge's attention, goodwill and benevolence. At the King's New School in Stratford-upon-Avon, Shakespeare received orthodox Roman rhetoric education and training. As a result, Shakespeare's writings are significantly influenced by his education and background. Shakespeare's work is dominated by courtroom plays, and he leaned extensively on the forensic rhetoric dramas plays produced between the late Elizabethan and early James I periods.

Jilan Wei | Who knows better: Corpus-assisted discourse analysis of 'I know' in the UK government announcements during the pandemic

This research aims to disclose who knows better during the UK lockdowns for the pandemic between two groups of speakers and illustrate the functions of the evidential marker 'I know' in the government announcements.

This research demonstrates that politicians use 'I know' more frequently than medical experts, especially during the second and third lockdowns and use this evidential in five constructions. Further analysis shows that two constructions for emotion-loaded expressions are adopted by politicians but absent in medical experts' speeches and that most of the five constructions rarely explicitly mention the information source. In short, politicians 'know better' than medical experts the power of 'I know' as an evidential marker for introducing a fact or an inference without worrying about indicating the information source and as an emotional switch for maintaining a dominant, resolute and compassionate stance.

Social media: <https://twitter.com/JilanWei> | I'd love to have a dialogue about: evidentiality, emotionality, stance

Day 2: 29th June

24th WICAL

TRANSCENDING DIALOGUES

DAY 2: 29 June 2022 | Online

8:00

Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 1)

Ranwa Khorsheed | Globalization & the Spread of English In Arab Societies: Syrian EFL students' Development of integrative motivation
Jerry XIN | Teacher-Researcher Collaboration on EFL Reading Materials Development: A Case in China
Leviana Vinanda | Investigating the strategies to incorporate a telecollaboration programme in an ELT classroom for adolescent learners

Discourse Analysis (parallel, room 2)

Bahareh Malmir | A Discursive Analysis of the Media Compensating Strategies towards the Stereotypical Representation of Islam and Muslims: A Critical Discourse Analysis
Katherine Hallin | Leader Trait Analysis in Russian: Translation and Coding

Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 3)

Guangxiang Liu | Inequality reproduction or habitus transformation? A Bourdieusian take on digital literacies of Chinese rural lower-class learners
Hanzhao Lin | "Don't call me teacher. I am just a student" EFL Visiting Scholar's Identities in Higher Education Teacher Development Program.
Maha Alhejji | Motivating language teachers through continuing professional development

Intercultural Communication (parallel, room 4)

Sundeep Dhillon | An exploration of the experiences of English for Academic Purposes (EAP) teachers working in the Chinese higher education (HE) context
Esperanza Espino | Sexting among adolescents: a new way of communicating sexuality - do boys and girls have the same risks
Alice Richardson | Interpreting and the asylum process

9:40

10:00

Keynote (main room)

Climbing and descending the 'impossible stairs' of critical research on intercultural communication
[Prof. Fred Dervin](#), *Professor of Multicultural Education, University of Helsinki*

11:10

11:30

Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 1)

Daniela Avello | Vocabulary learning through captioned-video viewing: The role of word-related factors
Yue Zhang | Understanding Language Learning Motivation and Investment: A case study of EFL Pre-service Teachers in China
Weizhao Gong | Chinese EFL Children's views on reading digital storybooks on Palfish App

Discourse Analysis (parallel, room 2)

Yanran Zhang | Television discourse: Analysing multimodal language in the Chinese child-directed and adult-directed broadcasting
Yang Liu | Navigating China's Identity in Combating COVID-19: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Chinese and Western Officials' Tweets
Ziqi Wang, Jinyang Chen, & Helin Li | The Biased Representation of Female in Chinese Murder Headlines in the Social Platform of Sina Weibo (MicroBlog)

13:10

24th WICAL

TRANSCENDING DIALOGUES

DAY 2: 29 June 2022 | Online

11:30	Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 3)	<p>Azadeh Emadi & Shaghayegh Hosseini Incorporation of digital literacies in the design of global ELT coursebooks</p> <p>Qiuxin Zhang Language Mindset and Emotion Regulation Strategy Use: Relationships to Undergraduates' Language Achievement in China</p> <p>Qin He The Roles of Verb Semantics, Entrenchment and Preemption in Chinese EFL Learners' Retreat from English Locative Overgeneralization Errors</p>
13:10	Discourse Analysis (parallel, room 4)	<p>Dongyu Zhang, Xintong Yao, & Kesi Huang Biased Gender Representation in Chinese High School EFL Textbooks</p> <p>Sameya Priom Language Alternation as a Scaffolding strategy in EMI Classrooms</p> <p>Abigail LaLiberte A Corpus Analysis of Queer as a Slur Discourse on Tumblr</p>
14:00	Lunch break (Wonder room)	Speed networking
14:00	Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 1)	<p>Yuhua Liu Comparing Computer-based and Paper-based Rating Modes in an English Writing Test</p> <p>Chenyu Yang Does No-Revision Indicate No Engagement? —A Multiple Case Study on Learners' No-Revision Operation with Written Feedback in EFL Writing</p> <p>Fatemeh kazemkhah Coping Strategies for Navigating Technostress During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Voices from Iranian EFL Teachers</p>
	Discourse Analysis (parallel, room 2)	<p>Helena Wall Exploring child agency in the negotiation of interactional norms in the primary school classroom</p> <p>Priya Prithiviraj Narrative macrostructure abilities in bilingual Malayalam-English children: a cross-language comparison</p> <p>Yiqian Cai Analyzing the Phenomenon of English-Chinese Intransitive Verbs with Objects</p>
	Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 3)	<p>Tianai Zhang Post-Pandemic Era: Students' Online Collaboration in Group Writing Tasks</p> <p>Shambhavi Singh Professional development needs of ESL teachers working in tribal schools in India</p> <p>Wenli Liu Perspectives of EFL Teachers in China on Schoolscapes: Perceptions and Practices</p>
	Discourse Analysis (parallel, room 4)	<p>Qin Fan Discursive value creation of sustainable fashion in Shanghai: A case study of 'klee klee'</p> <p>Jiaying Zhang A self-paced reading task: Investigating the impact of code-switching on text comprehension among bilingual students</p> <p>Vincent Wai Sum Tse & Alan Man Him Wong "The one and only in the industry": Ostentatious enactment of elitism in celebrity tutors' biographies</p>
15:40		
16:00	Keynote (main room)	<p>Language education and symbolic power: Dialogic perspectives</p> <p>Prof. Claire Kramsch, Emerita Professor of German and Affiliate Professor of Education, University of California, Berkeley</p>
17:10		

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 2: 08:00-09:40 | Parallel room 1

Ranwa Khorsheed | Globalization & the Spread of English In Arab Societies: Syrian EFL students' Development of integrative motivation

Studying the effects that globalization has brought on Arab youth from multiple perspectives -Psychological -Cultural -Linguistic This study tries to highlight the status of The English language with regard to world globalized realities, focusing on Arab societies in general and on the Syrian society in particular (Syrian Youths).The aim of this study is to examine the role of Youth culture in students' development of integrative motivation to learn the English language with regard to their habitual use of English multimedia taking into consideration their aspirations of a cosmopolitan self image.

Students original integrative orientations could be attributed to their sense of familiarity with the target language group (Clement & Kruidenier,1983). These feeling of familiarity and belonging to a greater cultural frame (pop culture),is the result of students contact and use of English media (Arnett,2002). One reason for being attracted to the international youth culture , is students' eagerness to acquire a cosmopolitan identity. Globalization's mediums (T.V, Internet), have compensated to a certain extent the lack of existence of a native English speaking community in Syria. Part of the students' possible & ideal selves was present in the recreated realities of English films' stories.

Jerry XIN | Teacher-Researcher Collaboration on EFL Reading Materials Development: A Case in China

Materials development is an essential part of language teaching as materials serve as a vehicle for input and practice (Richards, 2001). Since no published coursebook may satisfy all learners' needs, EFL teachers are arguably important materials-developers for their own students. Learning to design quality materials is thus imperative in teacher education (Tomlinson, 2016). However, previous studies focused more on materials evaluation than on teachers' professional development. To bridge this gap, the present study investigates whether and how teacher-researcher collaboration in China has an impact on EFL teachers' advancement in materials design for reading lessons.

Findings indicate significant changes in a teacher's ability to develop reading materials, notably heightened language awareness in selecting reading texts, greater attentiveness to learner needs, and strengthened pedagogical knowledge in facilitating learner progress in multiple skills. Findings also show that teacher-researcher collaboration is beneficial to teachers' development affectively, cognitively, and behaviorally. This sheds light on such collaboration being an effective way to support EFL teachers' pedagogical enhancement in materials design. Implications for this approach to collaboration in fostering teachers' overall professional growth will also be discussed.

Leviana Vinanda | Investigating the strategies to incorporate a telecollaboration programme in an ELT classroom for adolescent learners

The study is aimed to investigate the key strategies to integrate a telecollaboration programme in an ELT classroom, in relation to promoting learners' intercultural awareness. It is deemed crucial to provide learners with a critical attitude and flexible manner in managing intercultural communication within English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) contexts (Baker,2015). It is particularly relevant since research in ELF demonstrates how linguistic features and pragmatics are culturally embedded (Jenkins, 2013). In this sense, applying strategies to incorporate a programme beneficial to promoting learners' intercultural awareness is crucial to equip learners with skills relevant to the reality of the global use of English.

The study provides an example of how the telecollaboration programme can be effectively integrated into an English course. It unveiled a relationship between (1) strategic task design, (2) the chosen topic of lessons, (3) the varieties of tasks and digital platforms used during the programme, and (4) an explicit stereotype-related lesson to the raise of learners' intercultural awareness. It also revealed the potentiality of the telecollaboration programme to raise some elements in the model of twelve components of ICA suggested by Baker (2015, pp. 153-171) as well as the promotion of other skills such as digital literacy and linguistic skills.

Social media: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/leviana-vinanda/> | I'd love to have a dialogue about: intercultural communication, global use of English, teacher research

Discourse Analysis

DAY 2: 08:00-09:40 | Parallel room 2

Bahareh Malmir | A Discursive Analysis of the Media Compensating Strategies towards the Stereotypical Representation of Islam and Muslims: A Critical Discourse Analysis

Adopting a synergy of critical discourse analysis and corpus linguistics, this study aims at identifying the compensative discursive and metaphoric strategies used in the media to counter the existing misrepresentations of Islam and Muslims.

It is predicted that our findings can provide some convincing evidence that the media is taking serious steps towards compensating the stereotypical representations of Islam and Muslims. The findings will also present a classification of the major themes of the compensating discursive strategies used in magazines and discuss their importance in the media construction of Muslim identities as well as the implications for both media producers and users.

Katherine Hallin | Leader Trait Analysis in Russian: Translation and Coding

This dissertation both employs and critiques the methodology of LTA (Leader Trait Analysis) in order to expand the reach of such discourse analysis methods in assessing the personalities of Russian leaders. Because LTA was developed using English language vocabulary and grammar, its reliability when using foreign language discourse to discern leader personality traits is dependent on translation. In response to this issue, this research applies Mona Baker's translation studies criteria to assess the semantic equivalence, or maintenance of a discourse's original meaning, between the English translations used to create an LTA profile for Vladimir Putin and Putin's corresponding original Russian discourses.

Utilizing Baker's equivalence criteria, this study has identified that difficulties in maintaining grammatical equivalence are likely to influence how translated Russian discourses are scored in LTA. Putin's use of perfective past aspect in Russian was not reflected in the English translation and therefore his PsyCL score is likely to indicate lower than accurate scores on need for power and belief in ability to control events. Putin's PsyCL score on belief in ability to control events was also likely lower than accurate due to the frequent use of reflexive constructions in Russian. Lastly, the inflexible word order of the translated discourses probably produced inaccurately low PsyCL scores for multiple traits.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: Foreign Policy Analysis, Semantics, Translation Equivalence

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 2: 08:00-09:40 | Parallel room 3

Guangxiang Liu | Inequality reproduction or habitus transformation? A Bourdieusian take on digital literacies of Chinese rural lower-class learners

Given there is little scholarship on Chinese rural college students' realization of technological affordances and constraints in the university EFL environment, this study aims to explore how they negotiate restrictions and engage in varying digital literacies to reproduce inequality or transform their rural habitus to struggle for a legitimate rural status in institutional power relations. On this ground, drawing upon Bourdieu's theories of capital, habitus, and fields, this study seeks to answer questions 1) How do rural college students engage in varying digital literacies in the Chinese EFL context? 2) To what extent do these digital literacies shape their negotiation of rurality in power-loaden urban spaces?

Findings reveal that with the marginalized status in the institutional field as a result of their cleft habitus, Andy and Xu engaged in contrasting online literacy trajectories that contribute to or hinder the reproduction of their capital across online and offline spaces. It is also shown that habitus, as an evolving system of dispositions, features in negotiating their class constraints and directing diverse digital literacies. With the dynamic interplay of their habitus, capital in the online and institutional fields, they were able to negotiate different patterns of rurality reconstruction, with Andy being a competent and confident rural well-educated student, Xu still subject to his inadequate and marginalized positions.

Social media: https://twitter.com/gelya_cool_bb

Hanzhao Lin | "Don't call me teacher. I am just a student" EFL Visiting Scholar's Identities in Higher Education Teacher Development Program.

To better understand the interaction mechanism among identity, emotion and teacher agency, to show the rich complexity and dynamic process of the identity of visiting teachers through qualitative research, hoping to represent visiting teachers' lives vividly. The purpose of knowledge is to enrich the existing literature on teacher development for the lack of attention to this group, to give them a voice, and to innovate theoretical thickness and perspective. The purpose of the practice is to better understand the experience of the participants of the "visiting scholar" program in China, so as to improve the post-service training system of higher education, provide some opportunities for reflection on the design of the system in the future.

Visiting EFL teachers are not separated from their past identities and are still linked with their old habitus, but the new experience permits the possibilities of gaining new identities. Their identities are multiple and dynamic. EFL classroom is a site of struggle for identities and full of emotions. These teachers show great agency by employing strategies to construct, convey, resist, legitimize and negotiate their image and self-acclaimed positioning. However, when the teacher asks questions and opinions of them, the power of authority leaves no room for them to transcend the dialogue and this other-positioning leads to their emotional responses and identity crisis when the latent teacher identity become salient and foregrounded.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: teacher education/development, EFL teaching/learning, intercultural communication

Maha Alhejji | Motivating language teachers through continuing professional development

In a qualitative exploratory study, I designed a vision-based CPD program for language teachers in a Saudi college. It aims at investigating the feasibility and adaptability of Dörnyei and Kubanyiova's (2014) vision-based framework in motivating language teachers in a Saudi context, involving them in the process of localizing this framework through some CPD practices, and evaluating its impact on their teaching experience. Thus, the study will attempt to answer the following questions: 1. How feasible is Dörnyei and Kubanyiova's (2014) vision-based framework in motivating EFL teachers in a Saudi context? 2. How supportive have the target teachers found the intervention to their own motivation and teaching experience?

I hope that these qualitative instruments can help in exploring the application process of the vision-based CPD and gaining an in-depth understanding of its effectiveness in the research context. As recent L2 motivation research calls for applying 'a small lens' approach (Ushioda, 2016), studying vision and long-term motivation (Dörnyei, 2020) and conducting more longitudinal research (Ushioda, 2020b), I also hope that the findings of this study contribute to these areas and provide insight of how vision, social-contextual factors, and some CPD practices may interact and affect teachers' motivation. In addition, I hope that involving teachers in the process of a CPD program can help them develop their classroom teaching practices.

Intercultural Communication

DAY 2: 08:00-09:40 | Parallel room 4

Sundeep Dhillon | An exploration of the experiences of English for Academic Purposes (EAP) teachers working in the Chinese higher education (HE) context

The research aimed to explore the experiences of EAP teachers working in the Chinese HE context, from their motivations for choosing to teach in this context, the expectations of the intercultural environment, to the reality of their lived experience and how this experience can advise prospective EAP teachers who are considering working in that context. This research focuses on EAP teachers' perspectives of working within an intercultural context, something that is usually secondary to the experiences of international students in the literature.

Results indicated that EAP teachers were motivated to work in China by various intrinsic and extrinsic motivations. A range of expectations were considered including communication difficulties and institutional support, the extent to which these expectations were met in reality is also explored. The results indicated that cultural differences were expected and this was experienced in reality, particularly differences in academic culture. Overall, the sample indicated that although their experiences were mixed, they would recommend working in that context. Guidance for prospective EAP teachers considering working in Chinese HE is also provided, relating to ways of overcoming the challenges faced by the participants.

Esperanza Espino | Sexting among adolescents: a new way of communicating sexuality - do boys and girls have the same risks

Sexting is a new form of intimate communication in the digital society, referring to the exchange of sexually suggestive or explicit text messages, images or videos (sending, receiving or forwarding). Its normalisation among adolescents poses a challenge for society, as several studies suggest that this sexual practice is related to other risky behaviours and online violence. However, less is known about what circumstances increase the risk for boys and girls to engage in these kinds of behaviours. This study aims to address this research gap by exploring gender differences in the risk factors predicting sexting in boys and girls.

Specifically, cyberbullying, cyberhate, the need for popularity and, to a lesser extent, acceptance of romantic love myths and ambivalent sexism explained boys' and girls' involvement in sexting behaviours differently. The information obtained in the focus groups supported the quantitative results and some additional information was extracted. These findings highlight the need to design effective prevention and intervention measures to promote positive online communication among adolescents, including the exploration of sexuality.

Social media: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/esperanza-espino/>

Alice Richardson | Interpreting and the asylum process

The asylum process entails several interviews and hearings, at each of which the Home Office is obligated to provide the asylum-seeker with a competent interpreter. Yet when I was working as an immigration caseworker, many of my clients complained of inadequate interpreting, and reports reveal that the current provision of interpreting may be of concerningly low quality, so much so that some solicitors send their own interpreters along to court to monitor hearings. This project investigates how interpreting functions within the asylum process; • What role do interpreters assume; are they neutral messengers or allies? • Which factors affect interpreting quality? • To what extent can interpreters impact the outcome of the case?

The case studies have not begun, but I have conducted a pilot study which revealed the variety of roles interpreters adopt (the most common role is a 'conduit'), and how role choice can affect an asylum case. Poor-quality interpreting has major social implications; it could prevent an individual from effectively communicating their reasons for seeking asylum, thus damaging their chances of obtaining it. This project is therefore a crucial step in protecting individuals' Human Rights and access to justice.

DAY 2: 29 June 2022

10:00-11:10 | Keynote | Main room

Prof. Fred Dervin | *Professor of Multicultural Education, University of Helsinki*

Climbing and descending the 'impossible stairs' of critical research on intercultural communication

In my talk I use the metaphor of Penrose stairs (also known as the 'impossible stairs') to problematize the idea of criticality in research on intercultural communication today. The 'impossible stairs' consists of a two-dimensional staircase with four 90-degree turns which form a continuous loop. When one climbs the stairs, one could thus be descending them – and vice versa. This Sisyphean-looking illusion is called 'impossible' since it could not possibly exist. Here I want to use it as a (positive) metaphor to guide us in thinking further about some of the problems often found behind claims of criticality in research on intercultural communication, where the word 'critical' now appears to be omnipresent. I ask a certain number of questions for us to consider: What might it mean to do *critical research* on such a complex phenomenon and object of research and education as interculturality (a term I prefer to intercultural communication)? Inversely, what would doing *a-critical research* on intercultural communication refer to (no one ever declares that they do such research)? If most research on intercultural communication is critical, why do we still use the adjective? What seems to be hiding behind certain claims of criticality, which appear to be 'biting their own tails' and e.g. *essentializing essentialism*? How to promote perspectives that might lead to *criticality of criticality*, accepting to climb and descend the 'impossible stairs' of criticality? How could *criticality of criticality* reinforce *interculturalizing interculturality*? What is the role of multilingualism in this matter? I am hoping that my talk will make us unthink and rethink together what to do with the 'new normal' of criticality.

Fred Dervin is Professor of Multicultural Education at the University of Helsinki (Finland). Prof. Dervin specializes in interculturality in education, the sociology of multiculturalism and international mobilities in education. He has widely published in different languages on identity, the "intercultural" and mobility/migration (over 150 articles and 70 books). His latest books include: Dervin & Jacobsson (2022) *Intercultural Communication Education. Broken Realities and Rebellious Dreams* (Springer); Dervin (2022) *Interculturality in Fragments: A reflexive Perspective* (Springer) and Dervin, Yuan & Sude (eds. 2022) *Teaching Interculturality Otherwise: International and Chinese Perspectives*. Dervin is the series editor of the *Palgrave Studies on Chinese Education in a Global Perspective; New Perspectives on Teaching Interculturality* (Routledge) and *Encounters Between East and West* (Springer). Exploring the politics of interculturality within and beyond the 'canon' of intercultural communication education research has been one of Dervin's *idée fixe* in his work.

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 2: 11:30-13:10 | Parallel room 1

Daniela Avello | Vocabulary learning through captioned-video viewing: The role of word-related factors

Research has shown that L2 exposure is not constrained to formal instruction but progressively enhanced by learners' out-of-school contact (e.g. viewing), which seems to vary as a function of context and learners' characteristics (Muñoz, 2020). Hence, an increasing number of investigations have been conducted in the last decade to explore the effects of audiovisual input and identify the conditions required to maximize L2 learning (Montero-Perez, 2022). The present study attempted to fill the gaps in the literature as regards the extent to which extensive captioned-video viewing (11 episodes) fostered vocabulary learning in EFL primary school students, which is an under-researched age group (Montero-Perez & Rodgers, 2019).

The analyses indicated that the students improved significantly as a result of the treatment. Consistent with the literature, concreteness, frequency of encounters and word length were found to facilitate learning (Grabe, 2009; Puimège & Peters, 2019). Moreover, the students obtained significant gains as regards the words whose decoding better resembled the one-to-one correspondence found in L1-Spanish. Conversely, the participants, especially fourth graders, struggled to learn the words that were less consistent with L1 orthographic patterns, further supporting the idea that learners firstly assimilate and accommodate their L1 reading strategies and mechanisms to deal with L2 print (Perfetti et al., 2007) and learn from it.

Social media: <https://mobile.twitter.com/diag2000>; <https://www.linkedin.com/in/daniela-isabel-avello-garc%C3%ADa-12939441> | I'd love to have a dialogue about: young learners, audiovisual input, foreign language teaching

Yue Zhang | Understanding Language Learning Motivation and Investment: A case study of EFL Pre-service Teachers in China

Pre-service teachers (PSTs) in China are leaving the profession—their teaching beliefs rejected by experienced teachers (Yuan & Zhang, 2017), their voices imbued with authority and marginalized (Yuan & Lee, 2015), a poor public image of teachers as teaching machines and bottom-line factory-line workers (Teng, 2019). Becoming a professional teacher is a process of identity construction (Trent, 2010), and such identity shapes PSTs' language learning motivation (LLM) and investment in their language learning and teaching practices (Douglas Fir Group, 2016). This Ph.D. study aims to investigate how motivated these PSTs are to learn English and the extent to which these PSTs remain invested in multiple identities throughout the process.

Initial findings reveal that (a) PSTs of different socioeconomic statuses (SEEs) hold varied parameters of the teaching profession, imagine their future communities and positions differently, and have contrasting, thought-provoking perceptions and definitions of 'good learners', 'good teachers' and varying learning practices; (b) different ideological beliefs and parameters of the teaching profession shape PSTs' conflicting identities as sites of struggle, which exert influences on the extent to which they invested in various identityperforming practices; and (c) PSTs' successful and unsuccessful motivational dialogues reflect their fluctuating motivational trajectories while learning English to teach it as the target language.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: L2 Investment, Language Learning Motivation, Identity

Weizhao Gong | Chinese EFL Children's views on reading digital storybooks on Palfish App

Mobile devices have penetrated all spheres of human activities including education and mobile technology has taken language learning out of the classroom (Klimova and Polakova, 2020; Kukulska-Hulme, 2009). In China, with greater attention paid to English learning, mobile English learning apps designed for children are emerging. Palfish App, which provides original English storybooks with multimedia and interactive features, ranks first in the picture book category in China (according to the download number from App store). This study will explore Chinese EFL children's views on reading digital storybooks on Palfish App.

This study will shed light on children's independent reading experiences with storybook apps. It will contribute to the field of MALL by investigating children's English language learning with a mobile reading App in an informal context. This study attaches importance to children's voices. Their views concerning reading with story apps are expected to help us understand children's digital story reading experiences standing in their position and bring new insights for designing more motivating and helpful reading material for children in the future.

Discourse Analysis

DAY 2: 11:30-13:10 | Parallel room 2

Yanran Zhang | Television discourse: Analysing multimodal language in the Chinese child-directed and adult-directed broadcasting

Television provides an essential social media discourse. TV broadcasting is a unique recipient design and inherently multimodal. TV broadcasters, especially for children's programmes, are crucial for children's language learning. Research on television broadcasting for children mainly focused on child-directed language in western cultures, but has rarely studied it in the context of the Chinese culture. This study compared multimodal language strategies (prosody; linguistic features; gestures) in Mandarin child-directed and adult-directed broadcasting and explored how broadcasters' empathy related to their broadcasting language.

We found that: (1) Participants in the child-directed broadcasting had higher mean pitch, pitch variation, shorter utterances, more questions, more referring to their own name and audiences, and produced more gestures and gestures of higher saliency. (2) Empathy positively influenced participants' lexical diversity, frequency of referring to their own name, gesture frequency and saliency. (3) There was an interaction between participants' empathy and broadcasting programmes in many aspects (mean pitch, pitch variation, speaking rate, referring to the audiences, lexical diversity and gesture frequency). In sum, communication is multimodally audience-designed, and empathy plays a vital role in child-directed broadcasting.

Yang Liu | Navigating China's Identity in Combating COVID-19: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Chinese and Western Officials' Tweets

The political discourse on Twitter has become an essential aspect of presenting a country's national identity. With the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, the Chinese government has seized this opportunity to publicize China's anti-pandemic outcomes on Twitter and tried to construct a positive image in fighting COVID-19. However, some western government officials have committed to shaping public opinions against China and its achievements. Therefore, my study aims to reveal how Chinese officials manage their tweets to construct China's image under this crisis and how do they cope with the skeptical voices from some western countries. Furthermore, my study will unveil the ideologies and motivations hidden behind their tweets.

I argue that Chinese officials mostly appeal to logic and evidence in organizing their tweets. They also resort to emotion to resonate with people. Moreover, they have borrowed voices from others, making their tweets multi-voiced and well-supported. In their tweet discourse, they have presented a positive image of China via strategies like positive self-presentation of China, positive presentation of "affiliative-other"/"unified-self", and negative-other presentation of the opponents. Meanwhile, some officials in western countries have challenged China's performance mainly through negative-other presentation and manipulation strategies, such as stigmatization and scapegoating, which are mainly emotional and baseless orientations.

Ziqi Wang, Jinyang Chen, & Helin Li | The Biased Representation of Female in Chinese Murder Headlines in the Social Platform of Sina Weibo (MicroBlog)

Mass media has been a widely-discussed area of gender study, as some media strategies have fostered invisibility, stereotypes, objectification and stigmatization of women, which lead to a social bias against women development. Current studies on female representation in the media are mainly concerned with the gender situation in English-speaking or European countries, while little is known about the status quo of Chinese women as represented in the media. This study collects headlines of murder news from Sina Weibo, one of the most widely-used social platforms in China.

The findings reveal a strikingly prominent bias against women in the five categories. Specifically, compared with male suspects who are often excused by imposed causality, the headlines are more likely to use linguistic tricks (i.e. emphasizing gender) and unnecessary information (i.e. age and occupation) which provokes negative associations, to represent female suspects as evil or brutal; in contrast to male victims, females victims are significantly represented as the direct or indirect causer of the murder crime; even with co-suspects, more responsibility is attributed to women than men. The survey revealed that such headlines misled readers to establish a non-factual causal relation between women and the crimes in issue.

We'd love to have a dialogue about: news, gender, dialogue

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 2: 11:30-13:10 | Parallel room 3

Azadeh Emadi & Shaghayegh Hosseini | Incorporation of digital literacies in the design of global ELT coursebooks

In this study, we examine the elements of digital literacies in four global English coursebooks based on the revised framework of digital literacies. Doing so, the four most-used global coursebooks were thoroughly studied to find out the elements and components of the framework of digital literacies.

According to the findings, it has been revealed that each coursebook series includes the aspects in the framework of the digital literacies mostly in the focus on communication and collaboration. Furthermore, among the four series of coursebooks, American File, Touchstone, Four Corners, and then Interchange, in respect, cover various facets of digital literacies. The study can be helpful for coursebook writers and publishers to find the gaps in the present coursebooks and try to develop the new versions focusing more on the importance of knowledge of technology.

Qiuxin Zhang | Language Mindset and Emotion Regulation Strategy Use: Relationships to Undergraduates' Language Achievement in China

This study aims to examine the individual differences in undergraduates' language mindset, emotion regulation (ER) strategy use in English learning and the relationships between language mindset, ER strategy use and language achievement, then to develop a mediating model. Implications for English teachers to improve differentiated instruction and individual differences are discussed. This can also complement the studies of learners' language mindset and the ER strategies use in second language learning. To integrate information from an emerging line of research in psychology and education, namely, studies on mindset and emotion regulation, into the framework of SLA.

The findings showed that (1) growth mindset students had higher grades and higher levels of ER strategy use than fixed mindset students, both in terms of positive and negative strategies; (2) for growth mindset students, only the negative strategies of ability development, cognitive reappraisal, expressive inhibition, and deep breathing mediated the relationship between language mindset and language achievement. For fixed mindset students, there was no significant mediating effect among all kinds of ER strategies, which indicates that fixed mindset students use strategies at a much lower level than growth mindset students and they cannot use strategies to influence their language achievement as the growth mindset students.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: Language Teaching; Language Mindset; Positive Psychology; Learning Strategy

Qin He | The Roles of Verb Semantics, Entrenchment and Preemption in Chinese EFL Learners' Retreat from English Locative Overgeneralization Errors

Unlike L1 learners, L2 learners often do not seem to overcome learnability problems. Much previous research has shown that L2 learners do not acquire native-like knowledge of the locative alternations. Due to the cross-linguistic differences between Chinese and English, Chinese L2 learners have difficulty in the acquisition of English locative alternations. Therefore, the present study conducted two experiments to examine whether Chinese EFL learners produce locative overgeneralization errors and learning mechanisms behind Chinese EFL learners' retreat from English locative overgeneralization errors.

Semantic verb class hypothesis predicted that participants demonstrated knowledge of semantic constraints that prohibit figure-locative verbs from appearing in the ground-locative construction. A significant effect of entrenchment---whereby overgeneralization errors with high frequency verbs(e.g., *The waitress poured the bowl with soup) were rated as more acceptable than errors with lower frequency verbs (e.g. * The waitress ladled the bowl with soup) --- was predicted for every group. A significant effect of preemption--- whereby the use of a verb in the ground-locative construction constituted evidence that the figure-locative construction was not permitted--- was also predicted for every group.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: second language acquisition

Discourse Analysis

DAY 2: 11:30-13:10 | Parallel room 4

Dongyu Zhang, Xintong Yao, & Kesi Huang | Biased Gender Representation in Chinese High School EFL Textbooks

While the unequal gender representation in textbooks has become a focus of research around the globe, little is known about EFL textbooks in China. As high school has been a critical period to mould students' value, the study of textbooks in this period is of great importance. Therefore, this study aims to explore the gender representation of high school EFL textbooks in China. We selected the top 21 EFL textbooks published by three key publishers and collected data from texts, exercises and illustrations therein.

The findings reveal gender bias in both implicit and explicit ways. In terms of occurrence frequency, order of mention and narrative perspective, male-related expressions are much higher than those of female. Secondly, "he" is more frequently used as generic terms, showing stereotyped gender image. Also, profession profiles of male tend to be more diversified while those of female are confined to teacher and nurse. As for illustrations, not only the percentage of male is much higher, but the "male dominating image" is more commonly observed. Finally, invisible sexism is also hidden behind the seemingly neutral texts. This study reveals the gender bias in Chinese mainstream textbooks, calling for promoting gender equality in education.

We'd love to have a dialogue about: gender discourse analysis

Sameya Priom | Language Alternation as a Scaffolding strategy in EMI Classrooms

English as a medium of instruction (EMI) has been adopted in many non-anglophone countries to teach academic subjects. Research in this context has revealed that the implementation of EMI is not without difficulties. Bangladesh has also implemented EMI in some of its higher education institutions, despite the majority of students attending them not being adequately prepared to learn through EMI. This research investigates the question of whether, in this context, Bangla, the students' and teachers' native language, is used as a scaffolding strategy to ensure the comprehensibility of lectures. Furthermore, it also investigates what forms language alternation adopt.

I found two major patterns of language alternation: presentation-explanations and word clarification repairs (Gafaranga, 2021) to scaffold learning. That is to say, scaffolding occurred at every level. At the overall level, language alternation took the form of presenting lectures in English and explaining lecture content by using both Bangla (L1) and English (L2). At the local level, recordings of interactional data exhibit that the direction English - Bangla accomplishes the interactional task of content clarification. Following Gafaranga (2021), I have referred to the aforementioned language alternation as word clarification repair. From the findings, it is evident that Bangla is used as a tool to make the lectures more comprehensible.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: EMI, Bilingual, Scaffolding

Abigail LaLiberte | A Corpus Analysis of Queer as a Slur Discourse on Tumblr

The study examines the discourse around the debate over queer as a slur on the social media and micro-blogging site Tumblr. Users on Tumblr are 193% more likely to be a member of the queer community than any other social media site (Tumblr, 2021). The study draws upon Brontsema's (2004) history of queer, as well as Jeshion's (2020) types of reclamation. The research questions are: what kind of reclamation has queer undergone? how do people on Tumblr use queer, and who do they believe began the recent debate over queer as a slur on Tumblr?

In the corpus, queer is used as an adjective with its collocates, indicating it is not being used as a vocative. Posts tagged as q slur are used with collocates which warn of queer in the body of a post, indicating that even those who view queer as a slur will use the word. Finally, a collocational analysis of terf* shows a divide between those who believe that terfs started the debate, and others who dispute this but still tell terfs not to interact with posts which state that queer is a slur. This study is important as the debates among young queer community members may affect the research in applied linguistics that is only recently looking beyond the cisgender male homosexual community.

Social Media: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/abigail-laliberte-02080815a>; I'd love to have a dialogue about: Identity and Queer Linguistics

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 2: 14:00-15:40 | Parallel room 1

Yuhua Liu | Comparing Computer-based and Paper-based Rating Modes in an English Writing Test

The study, with mixed methods, compared raters' scores when assessing writing performance under the paper-based mode, and two computer-based modes (onscreen marking of scanned images and online word-processed version).

Results showed that the online word-processed version was significantly difficult than the handwriting versions. Besides, raters tended to be more consistent under paper-based Mode. The bias analysis found interaction between raters and modes but no interaction between the criteria and modes. Verbal report data showed that raters would read more iteratively under the paper-based mode than the computer-based modes. They had different attitudes towards the role of handwriting in writing and different preference towards the modes.

Chenyu Yang | Does No-Revision Indicate No Engagement? —A Multiple Case Study on Learners' No-Revision Operation with Written Feedback in EFL Writing

The present multiple case study focuses on the written feedback addressed with no textual change in EFL writing. It aims to investigate the process of learners' dealing with feedback before they decide not to revise their draft accordingly. It also aims to probe into the possible factors leading to their no-revision operations. This study intends to answer the following research questions: 1) To what types of feedback do learners make no-revision operations? 2) How do learners deal with the feedback before they make no-revision operations? 3) What factors might influence learners to make no-revision operations?

Expected findings are as follows: 1) The types of feedback addressed with no textual change are lexical, grammatical, semantic, discourse, mechanics, and rhetorical focused. 2) Preliminary sorting of the screen-capture recordings and interview data shows that some learners behaviorally engaged with certain feedback but consequently left the texts unchanged. They reported their confusion and uncertainty about how to change their texts according to the feedback, or doubt about the accuracy of certain feedback after consulting an online dictionary or their peers. 3) Learners' language proficiency, feedback actionability, and teacher training or intervention are the factors that lead to their decision to leave some of the feedback unaddressed.

Fatemeh kazemkhah | Coping Strategies for Navigating Technostress During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Voices from Iranian EFL Teachers

Language teaching is often listed as one of the most stressful professions and language teachers face a bewildering range of job-related challenges and stressors. The proliferation of online classes caused by COVID-19 have created a new stressor called technostress and teachers require to utilize coping strategies to deal with technostress. However, teachers' coping strategies against technostress has not yet been adequately addressed in the related literature on Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TEFL) in the context of Iran. To fill this gap, the present study explores the coping strategies teachers use in face of the stress caused by online classes in the context of Iran.

The results of thematic analysis indicated that EFL teachers typically used approach coping strategies such as acceptance, instrumental support, and planning while experiencing technostress. The findings also indicated that EFL teachers did not show tendency towards avoidant coping strategies while navigating the stress caused by using technology to teach English as a foreign language. The current study contributed to greater recognition of the coping strategies that teachers use. Finally, suggestions for further research are offered.

Discourse Analysis

DAY 2: 14:00-15:40 | Parallel room 2

Helena Wall | Exploring child agency in the negotiation of interactional norms in the primary school classroom

Oracy (skills in spoken language) is a life skill (Wilkinson, 1965), a medium of learning (Jones, 2017) and a facilitator of literacy and second language acquisition (Amorsen & Wilson, 2016; Pinter, 2017). However, in 2018 over 1.4m children in the UK were identified as having speech, language and communication needs (I CAN & The Royal College of Speech & Language Therapists); since which time, the reduction in face-to-face interaction during the Covid-19 lockdown has adversely impacted many children's oracy development (Henshaw, 2021). This study introduces the interactional sociolinguistics approach into oracy research in order to improve our understanding of classroom oracy norms.

In this presentation I discuss three excerpts, focusing on the negotiation of children's agentic learner roles. I frame my analysis with reference to the Early Years Foundation Stage early learning goals (Department for Education, 2017). My findings indicate a hierarchy of oracy norms, wherein the more flexible norms can be negotiated by children to create a more agentic performance of their learner role. Finally, I discuss the need to approach oracy teaching and assessment with a greater focus on child agency in the negotiation of oracy norms.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: interactional sociolinguistics, classroom discourse, oracy

Priya Prithiviraj | Narrative macrostructure abilities in bilingual Malayalam-English children: a cross-language comparison

The purpose of this study is to compare the narrative macrostructure across L1 and L2 in bilingual children learning English as a second language (ESL) and examine whether there is a cross-linguistic transfer of narrative abilities.

The results of this study may reveal cross-linguistic transfer of narrative macrostructure and provide valuable insights into the development of narrative abilities in bilingual children growing up in Malayalam-speaking homes learning English as a second language. The findings may have implications for mother tongue (MT) or home language (HL) use in classroom pedagogy as well as in home literacy engagement.

Social Media: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/priyapriithiviraj>; *I'd love to have a dialogue about: bi-/multilingualism, narrative assessment, cross-linguistic transfer*

Yiqian Cai | Analyzing the Phenomenon of English-Chinese Intransitive Verbs with Objects

This paper analyzes and compares grammatical structures, as well as investigates the actual learning situation of international students, using questionnaires and a corpus to determine whether second language learners from different language systems can understand and master the structure of the intransitive verb with object in Chinese, despite obvious differences in language systems. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the phenomenon of intransitive verbs with objects in Chinese from the standpoints of syntactic structure and cognitive linguistic theory, to gain a better understanding of this peculiar grammatical phenomenon, and to apply our findings to the study of contemporary Chinese language and language learning.

Finally, despite the impact of COVID-19 on the project survey, we discovered that students whose first language was not Chinese had varying levels of bias in their perception and acquisition of intransitive verbs with objects, owing to the negative effects of their mother tongue and different teaching methods. Most notably, the versatility of the syntactic structure of "intransitive verbs with objects" complicates learning Chinese syntax, which is already difficult in comparison to English. This leads us to believe that more study is required to further our understanding of the peculiar grammatical phenomenon known as "intransitive verbs with objects" and to apply our findings to the study of contemporary Chinese and language learning.

Social Media: 15864161888 (LinkedIn); *I'd love to have a dialogue about: intransitive verb; syntactic-semantic interface*

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 2: 14:00-15:40 | Parallel room 3

Tianai Zhang | Post-Pandemic Era: Students' Online Collaboration in Group Writing Tasks

Although interest in classroom interactional competence (CIC) has increased in recent years, learners' e-CIC and online collaborative tasks receive little attention. This study aims to investigate how students collaborate in nonteacher-supervised group writing tasks in online breakout rooms and how different degrees of online collaboration influence students' collaborative writings.

Firstly, without teacher supervision, social and emotional variables of learners' e-CIC (e.g. collaborative agency and willingness to give feedback) need to be mobilized more in online group work. Secondly, effective collaboration can provide students more second language learning opportunities in online nonteacher-supervised tasks.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: Sociolinguistics; Second language acquisition; Multilingualism

Shambhavi Singh | Professional development needs of ESL teachers working in tribal schools in India

Research on in-service ESL/EFL teachers' PD needs and the factors that shape the impact of PD remains scarce in teacher education literature. Generally, teachers' needs are assumed by external experts or elicited through a survey method. Such an approach often ignores teachers' individual needs in the process which is more acute in the case of teachers working in resource-constrained contexts (RCCs). In this connection, this study explores the perceived PD needs of ESL teachers working in tribal schools in rural India. The study also examines factors that can potentially facilitate and inhibit teachers' participation in and access to PD programmes in those contexts.

The findings reveal that teachers have varied PD needs that are intricately connected with their socio-cultural environment. The results also highlight the significance of adopting an enhancement approach – a more participant-centred and success-oriented approach – to identify the PD needs of teachers working in RCCs. The findings can inform the design of future PD programmes and especially, creating better PD opportunities for teachers working in RCCs.

Wenli Liu | Perspectives of EFL Teachers in China on Schoolscales: Perceptions and Practices

Schoolscapes help language acquisition. Previous studies have mainly analyzed mature linguistic landscape projects rather than conducted pre-research. In China, most empirical studies have focused more on schoolscales in higher education institutions than that in primary school, on the teaching of Chinese instead of that of English. Some studies have presented the pedagogical usage of schoolscales, but have failed to conduct empirical studies. Besides, research participants have seldom entailed teachers. Hence, this study aimed to explore the perceptions and practices of EFL teachers in three primary Foreign Language Schools in China's first-tier city Shenzhen, about bilingual schoolscales.

Findings indicate that the majority of EFL teachers: (1) had unconsciously noticed language signage on campus, and incidentally checked the correctness of translation and spelling; (2) believed that bilingual signage related to the internationalization and helped create an encouraging ambiance for students to speak English; (3) after this research, were aware of the roles of bilingual signage and approved the positive impact of them; some had used them in teaching. (4) were willing to use bilingual signage in teaching in the future; desired to co-construct schoolscales with students; were content with the current bilingual schoolscales and encouraged their schools to set more bilingual signage.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: linguistics, language teaching, education equality

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 2: 14:00-15:40 | Parallel room 4

Qin Fan | Discursive value creation of sustainable fashion in Shanghai: A case study of 'klee klee'

This study examines how Bourdieu's conceptualisation of distinction manifests itself in the promotion of fashion products that are regarded as 'ethical', 'sustainable' and 'authentic'. Adopting both ethnographic- and corpus-analytical methods, this paper aims to present how a Shanghai-based fashion brand 'klee klee' linguistically constructs the meaning of sustainable fashion, and discursively creates added value around its products. It highlights the significance of language in creating taste distinction and hopes to contribute to scholarly discussions on the role and value of language within political economies.

The mix-methods approach allows for methodological triangulation and provides a more comprehensive picture of klee klee's discursive value creation. This study reveals that through corporate branding, klee klee identifies itself with sustainable fashion and other like-minded stakeholders within the industry. It is argued that added value is discursively created through taste distinction and such discursive value creation helps the brand establish a niche market in Shanghai by differentiating it from other brands whose products rely on the industrial-, exploitative- and delocalized forms of production.

Jiaying Zhang | A self-paced reading task: Investigating the impact of code-switching on text comprehension among bilingual students

Code-switching (CS) is a common language style occurs in bilingual or multilingual speakers, and represents a phenomenon where two or more languages are present in the same discourse.. Most studies either only use single words or isolated sentences as reading test material, rather than the longer, semantically coherent text passages, those are way close to the natural reading behaviour in bilingual real-life. The aim of this study, therefore, was to examine the role of CS as an opportunistic strategy in facilitating text comprehension among Mandarin and English bilingual students with two measurable indexes, response time (RTs) and error rate (ERs) by a self-paced reading task.

Seventeen Mandarin-English bilingual students participated in the self-paced reading task. In line with the research purpose, it was hypothesised that the CS texts would somehow reduce reaction times and improve accuracy in text reading compared to other texts. However, no contribution of CS in reduction of response time was observed in this study. Another valuable finding regarding error rates is that once CS texts presented, proficient bilinguals instead reduced the accuracy of text comprehension. This study used an authentic, naturally generated corpus as material and explored the function of code-switching in a conversational setting. Nevertheless, the cognitive burden of bilingual readers in processing CS texts is somewhat neglected.

Social Media: <https://www.linkedin.cn/in/career/in/jocelynzhang-jiaying>; I'd love to have a dialogue about: discourse analysis, self-paced reading task, comprehension test

Vincent Wai Sum Tse & Alan Man Him Wong | "The one and only in the industry": Ostentatious enactment of elitism in celebrity tutors' biographies

In Hong Kong, a celebrity tutor is someone who has become famous for teaching fee-paying supplementary classes (also known as shadow education) at tutorial school chains. Previous discourse-analytic studies have identified the construction of celebrity tutors' overlapping identities for marketing purposes (e.g., Koh, 2016; Yung & Yuan, 2020). Aligning with recent sociolinguistic interest in elitism, defined as the discursive accomplishment of superiority, exclusivity, and distinctiveness (Jaworski & Thurlow, 2009), this study explores how celebrity tutors ostentatiously associate themselves with elitism.

Preliminary findings reveal that celebrity tutors evoke prestige affiliated with their educational pedigrees and flaunt the rarity and distinctiveness of their experiences and skills. While claims to elite status are discursively diverse, celebrity tutors cast themselves as simulacra of the neoliberal, profit-making self (Gershon, 2016). Their biographies display (generic) homogeneity in an attempt to produce differences on the grounds of knowledge, experiences, and other qualities. These biographies, as a promotional genre, not only present celebrity tutors as elites, but also intersubjectively encourage the target audience - students - to aspire to become elites in an educational system underpinned by meritocracy.

DAY 2: 29 June 2022

16:00-17:10 | Keynote | Main room

Prof. Claire Kramersch | Emerita Professor of German and Affiliate Professor of Education, University of California, Berkeley

Language education and symbolic power: Dialogic perspectives

Despite the ever greater ease with which we can connect and interact with others through face-to-face and online encounters, and despite the ease of access to past and present texts online, real dialogue with persons or texts seems to have become more and more difficult and risky. Exchange of information, yes, but dialogue? In our era of misinformation, fake news, politically correct slogans, and armed conflicts, how can we continue to teach language for communicative, or even intercultural competence? What should the goal of foreign language education be nowadays? Drawing on Bourdieu's notion of "symbolic power" (Bourdieu 1981) and Bakhtin's "dialogism" (Holquist 1990), I will try to recuperate the notions of *power* and *dialogue* from their all too facile reference to "participation and interaction" in the classroom to deeper principles of relationality (Kramersch & Zhang 2019) and symbolic action (Kramersch 2021) that are essential for students to understand the multilingual world around them.

Claire Kramersch is Emerita Professor of German and Affiliate Professor of Education at the University of California, Berkeley, where she taught courses in German and in Applied Linguistics, and where she was the founding director of the Berkeley Language Center. Her areas of interest are applied linguistics, language learning and teaching, language and culture, and bi- and multilingualism. Her many publications include *Interaction et discours dans la classe de langue* (Hatier, 1984), *Context and Culture in Language Teaching* (OUP, 1993), *Language and Culture* (OUP, 1998), *The multilingual subject* (OUP, 2009), *The multilingual instructor* (OUP, 2018 with Lihua Zhang), and *Language as symbolic power* (CUP, 2021). She is the past president of the American and the International Association of Applied Linguistics and the past editor of the international journal *Applied Linguistics*. She is currently the coeditor of two book series with Routledge and Cambridge University Press, and the editor of the *L2 Journal*.

Day 3: 30th June

24th WICAL

TRANSCENDING DIALOGUES

DAY 3: 30 June 2022 | Online

8:00	Keynote (main room)	<p>Resemiotization – an organizational semiotic approach Prof. Theo van Leeuwen, <i>Professor of Language and Communication, University of Southern Denmark</i></p>
9:10		
9:30	Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 1)	<p>Somayeh Damirchi The Effect of Jigsaw Reading Tasks on the Use of Cohesive Devices in Intermediate EFL Learners' Writing Xingyu Shi The Incidental Learning of Formulaic Sequences through Different Listening Modes Maricarmen Gamero Mujica Silence in Synchronous video-mediated language teaching: Teachers' Reactions and Responses</p>
	Discourse Analysis (parallel, room 2)	<p>Jiaxin Zhang A Study on Intercultural Communication Competence of MTI Students in the New Era Anita Beatrice Appartaim Ghanaian tertiary students' attitudes to accent of English in broadcasting and social media Yuqing Yang On the English Translation of Color Words in Du Fu's Poetry from the Perspective of Relevance Theory</p>
	Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 3)	<p>Jinwen Guo Advanced EFL Learners' Exemplar-based and Rule-based Processing Modes of Chunks via Reading News Text Jing ZHOU The use of gestures in classroom teaching : A comparison of expert and novice EFL teachers Simin Ren The Knowledge Exchange Process and Multimodal Speech Exchange System between Two Human L2 learners and a Digital System in a Technology-Mediated Real-World Language Learning Context</p>
	Intercultural Communication (parallel, room 4)	<p>Yesim Kakalic 'I don't want to get integrated!' Exploring the identification processes of offspring from Turkish German families against the background of mainstream discourses of social integration Wenrui Shi A Contrastive Study of Chinese and American Condemning in Politics – A Speech Act? Hongling Song Translating the Language of Tourism. A Corpus Based Study on the Translational Tourism Chinese Corpus in Iceland</p>
11:10		
11:30	Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 1)	<p>Siying Shen The Motivation for Learning Mandarin Chinese as a Heritage and Non-Heritage Language in UK Higher Education Samaneh Lahuti & Dr Zari Saedi The Large/Small Group Discussion Technique in an Online English Speaking Course During the Covid-19: A Scrutiny of Learners' Perspective Xueying Feng Research on the questions of novice TCFL teachers in one-to-one online teaching</p>
	Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 2)	<p>Narges Seydi Exploring the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and EFL Teacher Effectiveness: The mediating role of Teacher reflection Turaj Rahimi Iranian EFL Teachers' Attitudes towards and Strategies for Developing Autonomy in Young Learners Nusrat Gulzar Exploring the nature and role of the online MA ELT practicum in preparing student-teachers during the pandemic: data from a qualitative case study</p>
13:10		

24th WICAL

TRANSCENDING DIALOGUES

DAY 3: 30 June 2022 | Online

11:30

Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 3)

Yumna Aly | Blogging for Teacher Development: A Pioneering Practice of Metacognitive and Transactive Talk
Winnie Wai Lan Shum | A Preliminary Analysis: The Effects of Conversation Analysis (CA) on Students' Learning of Intercultural Interactional Skills
Diana Diaz | An investigation into the in-class emotions of non-English-specialist Colombian primary school teachers who teach English

13:10

Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 4)

Sachin Wanniarachchi | Understanding the Relationship between the Absence of Intercultural Education in Monastic Education and the Failure of Ethnic Reconciliation in Sri Lanka
Muhammed Vefa | Measuring the Levels of Burnout among the Displaced EFL and Non-EFL Syrian Teachers in Turkish Context and Liberated Areas of Syrian Context during the Post-Pandemic Era
Yizhuo Zhang, Siyue Chen & Qingyi Song | Chinese EFL Learners' Acquisition of English Relative Clauses: A Corpus-based Study

13:10

Lunch break (Wonder room)

Speed networking

14:00

14:00

Keynote (main room)

Transcending dialogues in language teacher development: Exploring practices for wellbeing and quality of life
[Dr. Judith Hanks](#), Associate Professor in Language Education, University of Leeds

15:10

15:30

Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 1)

Farbod Farahandouz | Multimodal cues in corrective feedback: the case of French as a foreign language classroom
Ha Nguyen | An Investigation of the Effects of Corpus of Contemporary American English on EFL Writing Self-Correction
Veronika Derecskey | Causes of EFL teacher demotivation in Hungary

Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 2)

Jun Jiang | The Comprehension and Production of English NP+VP+NP+AP Resultative Constructions by Chinese L2 English Learners — A study of dynamic usage-based models
Shuang Xu | Translanguaging in English Major's Online Grammar Classrooms: A Multimodal Ethnographic Study
Hoi Yat Daniel Pun | English Public Exams, Tutorial Classes, and Inequality: an investigation of small-scale English tutorial classes in Hong Kong

Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 3)

Roghayeh Pourbahram | University Students' Perceptions of Assessment Practices: Insights from TestTaking Narratives
Mahshid Kkamareh & Mohsen Shirazizadeh | L2 Writing Efficacy among Iranian English Majors: Do Gender, University Degree and Teaching Experience Make a Difference?

Language Teaching and Learning (parallel, room 4)

Yuki Komiya | Spectral and durational features of Japanese-native learners' English vowel production: A corpus-based acoustic analysis
Hoang Huynh | Rethinking the roles of silence and dialogue during non-formal online English speaking practice amidst the COVID-19 pandemic: A phenomenological autoethnography approach

17:20

Closing (main room)

[WICAL Committee](#)

DAY 3: 30 June 2022

08:00-09:10 | Keynote | Main room

Prof. Theo van Leeuwen | *Professor of Language and Communication, University of Southern Denmark*

Resemiotization – an organizational semiotic approach

This paper will introduce the emerging area of organizational semiotics, sketching its origins in collaborations between multimodal discourse analysts and scholars from the field of organization and management studies, and outlining its agenda.

It will then argue for resemiotization (Iedema, 2001, 2003) as a key approach to organizational semiotics, which needs to combine ethnography and semiotic analysis, as the stages of the resemiotization process result from the way organizational practices are organized and managed, and manifest themselves in particular uses of particular semiotic resources and in the discursive transformations this engenders.

The approach will be exemplified by a study of the practice of producing sexual and reproductive health information resources in a non-government Family Planning organization. Here written documents couched in specialized language are first resemiotized in 'Easy English' and in design briefs for graphic designers and audio-visual producers, and then into richly multimodal web pages, printed brochures, posters and videos produced for specific communities including Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islanders, culturally and linguistically diverse (CALD) communities and young people in both these categories. Analysis will focus on the way the organization's resemiotization practices make sexual and reproductive information more accessible and culturally appropriate, but also transform the information through specific deletions, substitutions, additions and rearrangements.

The paper will end by showing how resemiotization analysis may benefit organizations with respect to a range of practices.

Theo van Leeuwen has published widely in the area of visual communication, multimodality, and critical discourse analysis and was a founding editor of the journals *Social Semiotics* and *Visual Communication*. His books include *Speech, Music, Sound*; *Reading Images – The Grammar of Visual Design* (with Gunther Kress), *Multimodal Discourse – The Modes and Media of Contemporary Communication* (with Gunther Kress), *Introducing Social Semiotics*; *Discourse and Practice – New Tools for Critical Discourse Analysis*; *The Language of Colour*, and *Multimodality and Identity*.

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 3: 09:30-11:10 | Parallel room 1

Somayeh Damirchi | The Effect of Jigsaw Reading Tasks on the Use of Cohesive Devices in Intermediate EFL Learners' Writing

Writing is one of the most challenging language skills learners need to master (Nation & Macalister, 2020). One of the particular challenges of EFL learners with regard to writing is the use of cohesive devices. As Meisuo (2000) states, cohesion enables the reader to establish relevance between what was said, what is being said, and what will be said by employing appropriate, cohesive devices. In the jigsaw reading techniques, L2 learners need to put segments of a passage together and build coherence among different segments (Booker, 2021).

After collecting the essays at the beginning and end of instruction, a frequency count was conducted for cohesive devices in the writings. The total and individual frequency counts of all cohesive devices were fed in SPSS. Chi-square was used to examine whether there were significant differences between the control and experimental groups in terms of the number of cohesive devices they used in their writings.

Xingyu Shi | The Incidental Learning of Formulaic Sequences through Different Listening Modes

Previous studies suggest that the listening mode particularly facilitates incidental learning of L2 formulaic sequences, but comparative effects of different listening conditions remain underexplored. And although prior vocabulary knowledge is proved positively correlated with learning gains, little is known whether it produces difference across level-groups, a question vital to language teaching. Therefore, our study aims to address (a) which listening mode is more facilitating, listening-only or audio-visual; (b) whether effects are modulated by prior vocabulary knowledge at the group level. Importantly, the comparison sheds light on Mayer's (2014) Multimedia Learning Theory, whose prediction is being challenged by recent L2 evidence.

Based on Mayer's (2014) proposal that learning gains are maximized when both verbal (e.g., written and aural words) and non-verbal (e.g., graphs and pictures) channels of brains are activated, we predict that audio-visual input is more facilitating than listening. We also expect participants with higher vocabulary level to significantly learn more, given prior vocabulary knowledge is already proved positively associated with learning gains. However, we are currently open to results about under which MODE will which VABULARY LEVEL group gains more, as such an examination of interactional effects is new to literature and exploratory in nature.

Maricarmen Gamero Mujica | Silence in Synchronous video-mediated language teaching: Teachers' Reactions and Responses

During the pandemic outbreak in 2020, synchronous video became the preferred option for language teaching at different educational levels worldwide. The research publications about teaching during the pandemic have addressed the challenges of institutions, and education authorities, however, little reference has been made to the online practice of teachers and their challenges. The aim of the study was to understand language teachers' reactions and responses to the challenges emerging in their teaching via synchronous video.

Part of the findings show that the teachers perceived silence as more prolonged in synchronous video-mediated teaching than in face-to-face teaching. The silence gaps were more prominent when an interaction with the overall class was intended. The initial responses from the teachers represented an increase of TTT while restating their speaking turn. Finding the appropriate approach to handle silence gaps represented a learning opportunity for teachers, who tested different approaches that would fit their teaching style, the platform, and their learners.

Social Media: <https://mobile.twitter.com/gamero2606>

Discourse Analysis

DAY 3: 09:30-11:10 | Parallel room 2

Jiaxin Zhang | A Study on Intercultural Communication Competence of MTI Students in the New Era

Language is the basis of every activity in the world of countries, resulting in the crucial role of translation and interpretation. The MTI (Master of Translation and Interpretation) students is a huge group in China, with more than 300 universities established. Combined with the reality, it is not enough for MTI graduates to have high-quality language levels. The use of intercultural communication competence plays a pillar. This article is aimed to emphasize the importance of intercultural communication competence for MTI graduates in the new era, by analyzing the status quo of MTI students and the challenges of the future. At last, the article tries to put forward how to develop intercultural communication competence for MTI students.

The current MTI students' intercultural communication competence is good but not excellent. And most of them pay more attention to their language level than intercultural communication competence.

Anita Beatrice Appartaim | Ghanaian tertiary students' attitudes to accent of English in broadcasting and social media

A language enjoys as much prestige as the people who speak it and when it or its variety is despised, its people are despised with it. In the media, Ghanaians have indicated their approval for the use of Ghanaian English in institutions. Is that the same evaluation of prestige students who are usually tested on British English accent hold about Ghanaian English? This research investigates the attitudes of Ghanaian tertiary education students towards the various accents of English and in particular Ghanaian English. It further seeks to find out which accents, native or non-native, receive more positive evaluations and finally whether gender has an influence on the evaluation of accents.

The expected outcomes include the claim that Ghanaian tertiary students know and are able to identify among others Ghanaian English, British English, American English, Jamaican English, Indian English accents and locally acquired foreign accents (LAFA) in the broadcasting and social media. Secondly, native accents have both prestige and status among Ghanaian students although they have a positive and solidarity attitude towards the Ghanaian English accent and would prefer its use in schools and in broadcasting. Finally, gender plays a big role in the positive and negative evaluations of the accents in the different media some of the accents are raised positively based on the gender of the speaker. Ghanaians thus prefer Ghanaian English.

Yuqing Yang | On the English Translation of Color Words in Du Fu's Poetry from the Perspective of Relevance Theory

The poetry of Du Fu has been regarded as one of the representatives of Chinese culture of classical poems. Especially, Du Fu's Poetry characterizes unique color words attached with abundant culture connotations. This study attempted to investigate translation strategies of color words to reappear the mood in the target context and achieve the effective intercultural communication.

This study focused on the different English translation of "青"(green/gray/blue), "白"(white/commoner), "金"(gold/golden/metal). It is found that these color words attached with different cultural connotations in different textual contexts. Furthermore, the color words reflected Du Fu's ups and downs of life and expressed his concern for his country. In the English translating process, the translator fully considered the cultural connotations underlied color words and aesthetic expectation of target readers. The research contributed to intercultural exchanges through English translation.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: Chinese classical poetry

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 3: 09:30-11:10 | Parallel room 3

Jinwen Guo | Advanced EFL Learners' Exemplar-based and Rule-based Processing Modes of Chunks via Reading News Text

This study targeted advanced EFL learners' preference of information processing ways. Skehan (1998) proposes a dual mode model for language users to process information. One is exemplar-based mode, and the other is rule-based mode. An abundance of studies explored this issue since then. Various results have been shown and sometimes they seem controversial. One main disputable issue of them is: Are language users biased towards one mode? We focused on judging advanced EFL learners' preferences in this model when they processing chunks, and examined the roles that paper and screen mediums play in processing information of chunks when L2 learners reading news text.

The results indicate that for advanced EFL learners, the higher English proficiency they are of, the more adept they would be to use the exemplar-based way of processing, which is a native-like way. Besides that, advanced EFL learners' information processing mode might be more native-like when reading on screens.

Social Media: https://twitter.com/KingMoon_Guo; I'd love to have a dialogue about: SLA, Writing, Publishing

Jing ZHOU | The use of gestures in classroom teaching : A comparison of expert and novice EFL teachers

There is a growing interest in the role of teachers' gestures in education, and research has shown that students do benefit from teachers' gestures in subjects such as math, statistics and foreign language teaching. However, so far, few studies have focused on differences in gesture use between novice and expert teachers. This study investigated when and why novice and expert English teachers produced gestures in the Chinese EFL contexts. This study hopes to provide an in-depth understanding of gesture characteristics of novice and expert college English teachers and offer practical implications for language teacher education.

(1) both novice and expert teachers were likely to adopt beat and pointing gestures when teaching difficult or important information. (2) novice teachers tended to produce more pragmatic/interactive gestures when they had disfluencies or were nervous, whereas expert teachers produced more beat gestures when highlighting the knowledge points; and (3) novice teaches usually used pointing and iconic gestures to urge students to answer questions, while expert teachers usually produced metaphoric and pointing gestures to be interactive. In short, expert teachers seem to be more able to use gestures to handle classroom teaching and interaction.

Social Media: <https://twitter.com/amyjingzhou0923>; I'd love to have a dialogue about: language teaching

Simin Ren | The Knowledge Exchange Process and Multimodal Speech Exchange System between Two Human L2 learners and a Digital System in a Technology-Mediated Real-World Language Learning Context

L2 learners of Chinese in this study are immersed in a digital and technology-mediated, real-life language learning environment – a real-world digital kitchen context, using an online App – Linguacuisine on iPads, for guiding participants' cooking session and enable them to complete their tasks in a task-based language learning context. These learners are performing real-world task of cooking a real Chinese dish in a real kitchen, and they must interact with a digital system. This study will specifically looking at how exactly pairs of learners complete their tasks using which kind of multimodal resources while collaborating with a digital system to achieve intersubjectivity and epistemic progression for their L2 learning of Chinese.

This study contributes to 1) the unexplored area of knowledge exchange processes between two human participants and a digital system in relation to L2 learning tasks 2) the study of language learning processes and resource use in technology-mediated real-life environments 3) how different multimodalities are found to be used as epistemic resources for the participants to make epistemic move and achieve intersubjectivity.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: second language interaction; conversation analysis; multimodal analysis

Intercultural Communication

DAY 3: 09:30-11:10 | Parallel room 4

Yesim Kakalic | 'I don't want to get integrated!' Exploring the identification processes of offspring from Turkish German families against the background of mainstream discourses of social integration

The German media landscape is characterised by discourses of ethnic tension, migration, integration and assimilation in relation to Turkish German individuals and has led to a stereotypical and negative public image of this very group (Kontos, 2020). Such discourses typically construct and portray German Turks as 'the Other', ultimately intensifying discrimination (Bonfadelli, 2007) and feelings of alienation. This paper aims to give a voice to those who are targeted by these discourses and understand how Turkish Germans deal with and respond to mainstream discourses of social integration that contribute to this othering whilst constructing their identities.

Findings illustrate that although participants challenge mainstream discourses they at the same time orient towards power asymmetries reinforced by stereotypical discourses of Turkish Germans. They can only establish themselves in opposition to these discourses by reproducing the knowledge that is created by them and hence are 'trapped in the discourse'. Such discourses strongly influence the subjectification, self-perception and identity construction of (Turkish German) ethnic minorities. The study aims to enrich theoretical understandings of social integration as a discursive construct by shedding light on its strong link to identity and to 'de-silence' voices of marginalised and stigmatised groups and individuals.

Social Media: <https://twitter.com/yesimkklc?lang=en-GB>; <https://www.linkedin.com/in/yesim-kakalic-7619a257/>

Wenrui Shi | A Contrastive Study of Chinese and American Condemning in Politics – A Speech Act?

The aim of this research is to examine the discourse practice of condemnation in politics from a speech act perspective. Previous studies on condemnation have overwhelmingly focused on its linguistic realizations in daily language use by defining condemning as a strategy of the speech act of complaining, while the linguistic practice in the realm of political language use is relatively yet understudied. In this research we redefine condemning as a subtype of speech act of complaining in political language use. We also examine how media realises condemnation as political subjects in both Chinese and American data by deploying a bottom-up contrastive approach.

The similarities are: firstly, both of the two countries prefer the other-perspective to condemn, followed by the vague-perspective, and then self perspective is the least. Secondly, the frequency of upgraders is much higher than that of downgraders in the speech act of condemning in both countries' political media, which indicates that the political subjects in China and the United States tend to use more direct strategies to condemn others. For the differences, the most salient one is that there are significant differences in all dimensions of the strategies in both countries.

Hongling Song | Translating the Language of Tourism. A Corpus Based Study on the Translational Tourism Chinese Corpus in Iceland

This paper will present the results of a research project concerning corpora-based studies on the translated language of tourism. By employing a specifically designed corpus of translated tourist texts in Icelandic and English into Chinese and comparing it with a larger corpus of travel articles originally written in Chinese, the analysis aims to identify potential differences in the discursive patterns and stylistic features characterizing the translated language of tourism concerning tourist texts originally written in Chinese.

No research related to tourism Chinese corpus in Iceland has been done so far, which means this research will be of help to understand the extent to which the discursive patterns of translated texts might affect or not the communicative functions, linguistic properties, and persuasive effects typically employed in Chinese tourist texts, to provide an interpretation of the functions and features (including universals of translation) characterizing the translational practices of tourism discourse into Chinese, and improve the quality of the Chinese version of tourism-related service.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: linguistics, translation studies

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 3: 11:30-13:10 | Parallel room 1

Siying Shen | The Motivation for Learning Mandarin Chinese as a Heritage and Non-Heritage Language in UK Higher Education

This doctoral project will explore the motivation of Anglophone language learners of Mandarin Chinese over an academic year. It aims to investigate into the short and long-term motivation of 8 first-year undergraduates from a BA Chinese language programme in the UK (4 heritage language and 4 non-heritage language learners). The project resonates with the current call in the applied linguistics field for more focus on the learning motivation of languages other than English. Using a longitudinal research design, it will probe into potential similarities and differences in the motivational features of Chinese language learners with different backgrounds in a higher educational context.

Through tracking possible changes in students' identity and motivation over an academic year, the project would shed light on the perceptions of learning Chinese as a second and heritage language in higher educational settings. It will potentially offer policy makers and educators an insight into how psychological and sociocultural factors combine to inform the progress of heritage and nonheritage students of Chinese in formal educational contexts, how these influences may differ between the two groups, and how a supportive and inclusive learning environment can be created to enhance motivation and achieve desired learning outcomes.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: L2 Motivation; Identity; Qualitative Methods

Samaneh Lahuti & Dr Zari Saeedi | The Large/Small Group Discussion Technique in an Online English Speaking Course During the Covid-19: A Scrutiny of Learners' Perspective

Previous studies suggest that the listening mode particularly facilitates incidental learning of L2 formulaic sequences. Developing speaking skills has become challenging for English learners due to the lack of face-to-face instruction during the Covid-19. Researchers have proposed the Group Discussion Technique (GDT) to tackle the problem. Based on the number of students, the GDT can be applied on two levels: Small (SGDT) and Large (LGDT). Some studies have compared these two to identify one of them as the most efficient. However, there is still a gap regarding their benefits and drawbacks from the learners' perspective.

The findings showed that the drawbacks of LGDT from learners' perspective were less chance to talk, few dominate the discussion, passive listeners, and off-topic talks, however, the benefits were increased language learning motivation, deep conversation, and diverse ideas. The SGDT drawbacks included repetitive ideas, boredom, and stressful for shy students, while its benefits were meaningful discussion, building confidence, boosting creativity, and more chances to talk. The study bears several implications for instructors. Since learners' feelings affect learning, knowing the benefits and drawbacks of GDT from their perspective can help teachers better choose between the SGDT and LGDT based on the learners' needs.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: Educational Technology, Applied Linguistics

Xueying Feng | Research on the questions of novice TCFL teachers in one-to-one online teaching

Research on teacher questions in TCFL is traditionally focus on offline teaching. Some scholars have conducted research on teacher questions in online teaching during this pandemic. However, online teaching research is mainly about small classes of proficient teachers. This study, accordingly, aims to explore the questions of novice TCFL teachers' one-to-one online teaching, including the quantity and type of questions, and compare with the proficient teachers' small classes, so as to provide suggestions for the improvement of online teaching design of novice teachers.

Novice teachers, compared with proficient teachers, ask more questions in total especially response questions though they seldom answer questions themselves. It is also found that teacher questions' type is related to the texts selected. As for the unanswered questions, there are two circumstances: one is about teaching design, in which the questions such as "is this OK" sometimes remain unanswered; the other one is that the teacher may ask a series of questions and only one of which is responded by students.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: language teaching and learning

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 3: 11:30-13:10 | Parallel room 2

Narges Seydi | Exploring the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and EFL Teacher

Effectiveness: The mediating role of Teacher reflection

This study delved into the effects of trait emotional intelligence (EI) and teacher reflective practices (TR) on English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teachers' effectiveness (TE). The study also explored the mediating role of teacher's reflective practices in boosting the relationship between trait EI and teacher effectiveness.

The findings highlighted the pivotal role of the emotional intelligence has in teaching effectiveness and has highlighted the predominant role that teacher reflective practices can play in strengthening this relationship. In addition, the study is of significance to the administrators, teacher educators, and teachers interested in understanding the underlying psychological mechanism that could facilitate TE, particularly in the private Institutions. The study has added theoretical and practical implications to contribute to the body of research, for international and local contexts.

Turaj Rahimi | Iranian EFL Teachers' Attitudes towards and Strategies for Developing Autonomy in Young Learners

The notion of autonomy in language learning has been a prevalent topic of investigation over the last three decades. Despite the multitude of research conducted on examining autonomy in adult and high-proficiency language learners, there exists a scarcity of literature on this concept in young or primary-level learners. To fill the gap, the present study aimed to explore Iranian EFL teachers' beliefs about and techniques for developing autonomy in young learners aged 9 to 12.

The results revealed that teachers perceived autonomy development in young language learners as a crucial characteristic, although, they asserted that this feature needs to be nurtured under the appropriate supervision of competent instructors. Additionally, teachers' recommended strategies to foster autonomy in young learners included out-of-class-learning encouraging, technology-related, learner-related, and instructional strategies. The findings of this study highlight that the reinforcement of autonomy in young language learners is desirable, can lead to more confidence in the learning process, and have the potential to be conducive to higher educational achievement in the future.

Nusrat Gulzar | Exploring the nature and role of the online MA ELT practicum in preparing student-teachers during the pandemic: data from a qualitative case study

This study highlights the findings of a qualitative case study that looked at the benefits of introducing various tasks in the online practicum, also known as e-practicum, in an MA ELT programme at a public institution in Bangladesh. The key purpose is to shed light on the various student-centered activities and strategies that can be implemented online as part of the practicum to help pre-service teachers build their classroom preparedness as well as their digital competence. It also goes over how teachers develop the capacity to manage virtual relationships with their teacher and peers during their practicum preparation and performance, as well as in their WhatsApp group.

The analysis of the findings will be done by employing the following techniques: 1. Content analysis will be done to interpret the WhatsApp discussions, written comments to peers, and recorded peer teaching sessions 2. Data from the focus group interviews will be thematically analysed to understand their views regarding their new experience. 3. Data from the brief reflective notes from the researcher, who conducted and supervised peer teaching lesson plans and sessions with her MA students for the first time, will also be used for triangulation and interpretation.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: English Language Teacher Education and Development, Instructional Technologies and English for Academic Purposes (EAP)

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 3: 11:30-13:10 | Parallel room 3

Yumna Aly | Blogging for Teacher Development: A Pioneering Practice of Metacognitive and Transactive Talk

WICAL sends an invitation to transcend dialogues in various domains including teacher development. Probing into this area, collaborative talk tops recent methods that focus on analytical thinking. Yet, many teachers find barriers in their dialogic space with their peers or mentors. Accordingly, this study aims at exploring how blogging can help teachers in my context promote their metacognitive and transactive talk through posting and commenting. The purpose of this experience is to hone the teachers' metacognitive skills and transactive interaction. Through blogging, teachers will use transactive statements, questions and responses to critique, ask for clarification or justify ideas.

Thus, it is expected that unearthing the metacognitive and transactive talks will enhance CD of the teachers through blogging. The longer time span in blogging than the dialogic CD helps teachers to reflect, re-examine beliefs and search for new techniques and methodologies. Besides, blogging should positively affect the smooth transition through the stages and the moves of CD. Furthermore, it psychologically supports novice and unconfident teachers. To conclude, this presentation is relevant to teachers and managers who look for designing future PD plans. Researchers will be also provided with some insights for future tools of integrating technology with teacher education.

Social Media: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/yumna-muhammed-aly-177a2680/>; I'd love to have a dialogue about: multilingualism, Intercultural communication and teacher training

Winnie Wai Lan Shum | A Preliminary Analysis: The Effects of Conversation Analysis (CA) on Students' Learning of Intercultural Interactional Skills

To bridge the learning of both language and culture, the concept of CA is being incorporated into the pedagogy and teaching materials design of an intercultural interaction short course (IISC). The current study reports on the preliminary analysis of the effects of CA on students' intercultural language learning after taking the short course. Specifically, the study will examine 1) how learners used CA to make sense of their intercultural encounters, and 2) the benefits and challenges experienced by the learners using CA.

The preliminary analysis of the data collected showed that some learners experienced difficulties when using CA, while some were able to use CA in various ways and degrees to help them understand their intercultural experiences. Although this finding shows the possible challenges CA might encounter as a pedagogical tool for intercultural language learning, it also indicates the potential of CA and points a way forward for improvement.

Social media: <https://twitter.com/WinnieS63143516>; <https://www.linkedin.com/in/winnie-shum-2a458657/>; I'd love to have a dialogue about: Intercultural language teaching and learning, Conversation Analysis, Pedagogy

Diana Diaz | An investigation into the in-class emotions of non-English-specialist Colombian primary school teachers who teach English

Bilingualism has become a key policy objective for non-English speaking countries like Colombia. Governments have stated that English should be taught from primary level and have given this responsibility to the form teacher who must teach all subjects. Primary teachers are not English teachers and may not even know the language. This research seeks to understand the in-class emotions and emotional displays of primary teachers who have been instructed to teach English without training or English teaching experience. Questions include: what emotions do primary teachers who lack L2 expertise experience feel when teaching English in the Colombian primary school classroom? What triggers these emotions? How do teachers perform emotional labour?

As the research is still in its pilot stages, conclusive data has not yet been collected. What has been observed is that teachers suffer from foreign language anxiety for not being proficient in the language, as well as from foreign language teaching anxiety for having to teach a language they have not been trained to teach. Teachers with higher levels of proficiency and who like English feel less anxious with the task, while teachers with low levels of proficiency feel overwhelmed by it and use emotion regulation strategies. Many of these strategies have to do with modifying the situation or deploying attention from it (Jacobs & Gross, 2014), by not teaching English or by teaching English in Spanish.

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 3: 11:30-13:10 | Parallel room 4

Sachin Wanniarachchi | Understanding the Relationship between the Absence of Intercultural Education in Monastic Education and the Failure of Ethnic Reconciliation in Sri Lanka

While impeding the much needed cognitive dimension of intercultural communication, the ESL textbook prescribed for the monastic education in Sri Lanka violates many national goals of education. This paper investigates the interrelation between the non-representation of the intercultural and interfaith dialogue in monastic education and the failure of ethnic reconciliation in post-war Sri Lanka. A blatant dearth of intercultural education in the ethnocentric monastic education of the Sinhala Buddhist monk, to whom the dominant ideology of Sri Lanka, Sinhala Buddhism, provides a hospitable space to bolster Sinhala Buddhist monk's authority further to monopolize not only the Sinhala Buddhists but also the non-Sinhala Buddhists while resisting.

It was understood that the Sinhala Buddhist monks' "obliviousness" to the culture(s) of the other is a major issue leading to the deferred ethnic reconciliation in Sri Lanka and the need to introduce lessons that address the realities of the local minorities whose identities are deliberately discounted. Thus, the necessity to integrate lessons which promote interethnic understanding is understood imperative to establish ethnic reconciliation in Sri Lanka.

Social Media: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/sachin-anushka-wanniarachchi-47771233/?originalSubdomain=lk>; I'd love to have a dialogue about: Intercultural Education, ethnocentrism, second language teaching

Muhammed Vefa | Measuring the Levels of Burnout among the Displaced EFL and Non-EFL Syrian Teachers in Turkish Context and Liberated Areas of Syrian Context during the Post-Pandemic Era

Throughout the past decade language teachers have faced a considerable number of dilemmas to cope with the ongoing and ever-rapid changes in the middle east area. This has directly reflected on teachers' performance, level of teacher education, training related to teacher development, teacher's psychological identity, and other mental and psychological factors. The most influenced teachers by the addressed points are displaced EFL teachers who have altered their original territories and transferred to the northern part of Syria and Turkey. Those teachers suffered from different multi-faceted crises owing to the variables related to their situations.

The potential findings are supposed to assist EFL and non-EFL teachers who are working in the educational context in areas of conflict or areas or being displaced teachers to have a higher level of awareness to decrease the levels of burnout.

Social Media: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/muhammed-vefa-14138a127/>; I'd love to have a dialogue about: Displacement, Teacher identity, Burnout, Teacher burnout, Burnout Strategies

Yizhuo Zhang, Siyue Chen & Qingyi Song | Chinese EFL Learners' Acquisition of English Relative Clauses: A Corpus-based Study

The relative clause is a fruitful area in the field of L2 learning (Cook, 1993). To predict the difficulty order of learning relative clauses (RC), three major hypotheses were made: Noun Phrase Accessibility Hierarchy (NPAH) (Keenan & Comrie, 1977), Perceptual Difficulty Hierarchy (PDH) (Kuno, 1974) and SO Hierarchy Hypothesis (SOHH) (Hamilton, 1994). An increasing amount of research has tested these three hypotheses. While most studies focused on the RCs produced in elicitation tasks, the RCs in the natural context seem to be neglected. Furthermore, the connection between language learners' L1 and L2 remains a potential area for research. Thus, the current research aims to examine the L2 learner's acquisition of RC by translational texts.

The findings not only stress methodological implications in corpus-based RC research, but also highlight the value of establishing the connection between learners' L1 and L2. It also suggests that the non-restrictive relative clause (NRR), which has been neglected in RC studies, may be a potentially significant subject in L2 research.

Dr. Judith Hanks | *Associate Professor in Language Education, University of Leeds*

Transcending dialogues in language teacher development: Exploring practices for wellbeing and quality of life

Traditionally, dialogues of research in applied linguistics have positioned teachers, teacher educators and learners (i.e. practitioners) as objects or subjects of research rather than as co-researchers capable of

Judith Hanks has worked as a language teacher, teacher educator, researcher and lecturer in China, Italy, Singapore and the UK. Over the past 20 years, she worked with colleagues from Brazil, China, Japan and the UK to develop a framework of principles for practitioner research for language teachers and learners. This culminated in: *The Developing Language Learner: an introduction to Exploratory Practice* (Allwright & Hanks, 2009), and her most recent book: *Exploratory Practice in Language Teaching: Puzzling about principles and practices* (Hanks, 2017). Judith's research interests lie in the areas of practitioner research in applied linguistics, teacher education and wellbeing, professional development, and intercultural issues in language education. She is co-convenor of the international [AILA Fully Inclusive Practitioner Research Network](#).

You can read more about her recent projects 'Sticky Objects and pathways to wellbeing' (2020) [here](#) and 'Teacher wellbeing and burnout: understanding the causes' (2021) [here](#).

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 3: 15:30-17:10 | Parallel room 1

Farbod Farahandouz | Multimodal cues in corrective feedback: the case of French as a foreign language classroom

All learners make errors in learning a new language. For teachers as well as researchers in applied linguistics and classroom interaction analysis, making language errors (syntax, phonetic or lexical) is a necessary step to learning. In our study we try to show how teachers use multimodal elements such as gesture, gaze, facial expressions, and body posture to give corrective feedback to language learners in classroom interaction. Once we identified these aspects, we try to understand the underlying pattern of the usage and examine the teachability of multimodal feedback in teacher training courses.

We expect to see different forms of gestures as corrective feedback during classroom interaction. We think that the nature of the error and the degree of correctness/incorrectness play an important role in teachers' use of multimodal elements. Besides, interrupting someone for corrective feedback may have some cultural (politeness/impoliteness) and psychological (stress/emotion) reactions that could push teachers to avoid using verbal feedback.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: gesture, multimodality, classroom interaction, corpus linguistics and music

Ha Nguyen | An Investigation of the Effects of Corpus of Contemporary American English on EFL Writing Self-Correction

The research conducted a small-scale study at a University in Vietnam to examine how well corpus can be used as guidance to assist English majors' in the process of essay self-revision. The researcher aimed to explore students' attitudes towards the use of a corpus as well as their evaluations of the advantages and disadvantages of using the corpus to correct lexicogrammatical errors in writing. The instrument chosen for the study was the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA), one of the largest and freely available corpora of English at present.

The findings from this study reveal that the strengths of COCA outweigh its weaknesses. Some advantages include its user-friendly interface, its large number of sample sentences, or pieces of authentic language. Yet disadvantages such as technological malfunctions, time-consuming procedures of data interpretation, or difficulties in solving complicated errors. Despite the drawbacks of COCA, students still expressed an overall positive attitude towards the corpus and consider it to be a useful tool for future essay self-correction.

Veronika Derecskey | Causes of EFL teacher demotivation in Hungary

In recent decades, teacher motivation and demotivation has become increasingly important in research. In an ever-changing world, education is also undergoing constant change. As a result, a language teacher today is exposed to a number of positive and negative influences on a daily basis within the walls of classrooms. My qualitative study aimed to explore the positive and negative feelings of current English teachers in Hungary about teaching and to explore the possible solutions and coping techniques suggested by teachers for the phenomenon of demotivation or even burnout that is already developing.

Both motivating and demotivating factors reported by teachers were grouped based on Bronfenbrenner's Ecosystems Theory (1979): the microsystem with the direct environment of the individual, the mesosystem, which is the influence of other systems, the exosystem, meaning the indirect environment of the individual, and the macrosystem, including social and cultural influences (Bronfenbrenner, 1979, 2005). The results shed light on a number of factors that can influence motivation not only negatively but also positively, and some coping suggestions reported by participating teachers.

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 3: 15:30-17:10 | Parallel room 2

Jun Jiang | The Comprehension and Production of English NP+VP+NP+AP Resultative Constructions by Chinese L2 English Learners —A study of dynamic usage-based models

Studies on the second language acquisition of English resultative constructions usually classify verbs into unaccusative and unergative verbs, and thus do not include the case of transitive verbs followed by non-selective object resultative constructions and unergative verbs followed by fake objects resultative constructions. They didn't consider the frequency factor, let alone explored the information processing factors and their dynamic development process. This study aims to the comprehension and production of 3 kinds of resultative construction subtypes, and their information processing factors and the dynamic development process.

It was predicted that comprehension of the English NP+VP+NP+AP resultative constructions was influenced by construction types, proficiencies, and frequencies. The output of resultative constructions was not so satisfactory, mostly influenced by L1's syntactics and semantics, and cognitive strategies. Learners mostly had associative learning, with only advanced level learners extending to rule-based learning for some constructions with specific token frequencies or verbs. Structural priming greatly facilitated the acquisition of each type of resultative constructions to different degrees.

Shuang Xu | Translanguaging in English Major's Online Grammar Classrooms: A Multimodal Ethnographic Study

There is an increasing interest in the topic of translanguaging in language teaching classrooms in the recent twenty years, and most of the research focuses on the nature of translanguaging practices in content learning. However, few studies specify how translanguaging strategies are used in online classes in higher education to foster ELT. This thesis investigates the following questions: 1) What are the pedagogic work modes in online English grammar classrooms? 2) How is translanguaging realized by Chinese English Language teachers in English grammar classrooms? 3) What are the students' attitudes toward adopting translanguaging in their classrooms?

The research demonstrates pedagogical work of modes, and three main translanguaging strategies, which are the explain strategy, manage strategy, and co-learning strategy. Through interviews, this thesis gets a better understanding of how the students' former learning experience, socio-cultural backgrounds, and identities influence their translanguaging activities. Upon this, this study summarizes three main positives of adopting translanguaging —bridging the knowledge gap, narrowing down social distance, and building identity. At the same time, translanguaging also faces great challenges from the goal formation and confusion it creates in communication.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: translanguaging; online learning; multimodality

Hoi Yat Daniel Pun | English Public Exams, Tutorial Classes, and Inequality: an investigation of small-scale English tutorial classes in Hong Kong

The English tutoring industry and its impact on formal schooling in Hong Kong have been extensively discussed, both academically and in mass media. Yet the focus has normally been on large-scale tutorial centres, where the tutor 'kings and queens' are often the centres of attention. Due to the double impact of the pandemic and high land rent, there has been a decline in the large-scale tutorial chain stores, and small-scale classes given by lesser-known tutors have been emerging in return. This raises new issues from various aspects, such as the pricing and the quality of the tutors, information cost of the tutees, what English skills are taught and learnt, etc. There is a need to address them.

This presentation discusses the small-scale English tutorial classes from a political economy perspective. By examining the roles of tutors, tutees, and English in the tutorial lessons as a set of social-linguistical practice, it seeks to reveal the underlying principles that sustain, or even worsen, the existing inequality in Hong Kong. It is argued that HKDSE takers may become disadvantaged regardless of their English proficiency. The presentation also includes a discussion on how HKDSE takers perceive English learning when they are at tertiary education stage.

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Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 3: 15:30-17:10 | Parallel room 3

Roghayeh Pourbahram | University Students' Perceptions of Assessment Practices: Insights from TestTaking Narratives

The perceptions that learners possess towards tests, can influence their learning outcomes directly and lead to productive or mal-productive learning behaviors. There is, however, limited research on students' views of assessment practices, especially in a higher education context, a gap that requires further attention by scholars. To this end, the current qualitative study attempted to gain an in-depth insight into university students' views and perspectives towards assessment by asking them to write test-taking narratives.

Fear, stress, anxiety, and other negative feelings were associated with the participants' first test-taking experience and UEE. UEE was the most important exam in participants' life, affecting their future. However, all the negative feelings of the world could be associated with it. Too much stress and pressure were what the participants felt regarding this assessment tool. It seems that the corresponding exam is not designed to cater to different features of standard tests; and considering exam results, it biases a group over others. The paper also identified key problems in the language exams students had previously taken. Overall, most of the exams (especially those based on speaking) had problems with regard to the validity.

Mahshid Kkamareh & Mohsen Shirazizadeh | L2 Writing Efficacy among Iranian English Majors: Do Gender, University Degree and Teaching Experience Make a Difference?

L2 writing efficacy plays a significant role in writing performance especially in EFL contexts where writing competence is usually overshadowed by speaking proficiency and sources of motivation are scarce. Given the paucity of research on this variable, the present study examines the effect of gender, university degree and teaching experience on L2 writing efficacy among Iranian university students majoring in English.

Our results showed that there is no difference in L2 writing efficacy between males and females. University degree, however, made a significant contribution to writing self-efficacy as PhD holders were found to be more efficacious in L2 writing than MA holders who were in turn more efficacious than BA holders. One-way ANOVA also revealed that participants with high experience in teaching English felt more efficacious in L2 writing than mid-experience participants who were, in turn, more efficacious than low-experience participants. Our findings suggest that L2 writing efficacy is rooted in multiple sources and that, in general, further exposure to instruction both as a teacher and a student can promote writing efficacy in EFL contexts.

I'd love to have a dialogue about: Writing self-efficacy

Language Teaching and Learning

DAY 3: 15:30-17:10 | Parallel room 4

Yuki Komiya | Spectral and durational features of Japanese-native learners' English vowel production: A corpus-based acoustic analysis

Pronunciation is a challenging aspect for most English learners (Saito, 2007). Nevertheless, pronunciation still receives little pedagogical attention and teaching/learning approaches are underdeveloped (Pennington & Rogerson-Revell, 2019). In order to better inform pronunciation teaching/learning, this study focuses on vowels, aiming to identify the spectral (formant frequencies) and durational (length) features of Japanese-native learners' English vowel production. While studies have commonly used controlled word-reading tasks, this study used unscripted monologue data in a spoken English corpus, to increase the sample size and generalisability to naturalistic speech contexts.

As a result, the JPN speakers' overall vowel space was significantly larger than the ENS speakers', suggesting that they do not "reduce" vowels in fast speech as native speakers do. Also, the learners exhibited consistent mergers of spectrally close vowels (/ɪ i:/, /ʊ u:/, /ʌ æ/ and /ɑ æ/) which are non-contrastive in their first language. Furthermore, the learners significantly exaggerated the durational differences between the merged vowels compared to the native speakers, presumably in order to help contrast the vowels that could not be fully distinguished by formant frequencies. The findings carry practical implications for the learning/teaching of English vowel segmental features.

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Hoang Huynh | Rethinking the roles of silence and dialogue during non-formal online English speaking practice amidst the COVID-19 pandemic: A phenomenological autoethnography approach

The use of silence and spoken dialogue in English-delivered online synchronous platforms has been extensively studied as a means of assisting language learners in developing their linguistic and communication skills. However, an under-researched area is understanding how English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners encounter and use silence as a pedagogical tool during their interactions in non-formal online learning. This study used Bao's (2021) RADAR framework and positioning theory to examine the researcher's experiences with silence and talk during Zoom meetings hosting 15 to 20 EFL learners practising English speaking skills in Vietnam.

The study discovered that silence and talk both contribute pedagogically and conceptually to learners' growth of English-speaking abilities, with particular attention paid to four forms of engagement: content-learner, learner-learner, learner-moderator, and technology-learner. While the link between talk and silence is obvious, strategic planning should also be well-executed in order to minimise unneeded periods of negative silence and talk. These findings offer new perspectives on our current understanding of how such silence-talk relationships in online synchronous interactions should be understood cautiously, considering their circumstances.

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